

Iridium-Catalyzed Asymmetric Hydrogenation of Unsaturated Oxime Ethers as a Relay towards Chiral Aldehydes

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Abstract

Iridium catalysis is under the spotlight in terms of its utility in asymmetric hydrogenation reactions. Beginning as one of the few catalytic systems able to hydrogenate unfunctionalized olefins with excellent reactivity and selectivity, in the past two decades, iridium catalysts bearing chiral ligands have established themselves as indispensable tools for inducing chirality on functionalized olefins, carbonyls, and even imines. A multitude of unsaturated carboxylic acid derivatives, allylic alcohols, and other conjugated olefins have been successfully reduced by iridium chiral catalysts, except for unsaturated aldehydes. Stemming from the limited reports on the asymmetric hydrogenation of these types of substrates and the fact that chiral saturated aldehydes are of use in industry as fragrances, in the herein report, we investigate the challenges behind the direct asymmetric hydrogenation of unsaturated aldehydes and present the synthesis of a library of novel prochiral α,β -unsaturated oxime ethers, which have shown to be readily hydrogenated using known and efficient iridium-N,P chiral catalysts. A fast ozonolytic cleavage of the oxime ether functionality is then suggested to serve as a tool for generating the corresponding saturated chiral aldehydes with retention of the installed chirality.

Popular Science Description in Swedish

Handslaget är en internationell symbol för ömsesidigt engagemang för en given ed. Men för att två personer ska kunna skaka hand måste de båda använda antingen höger eller vänster hand. Att använda en höger- och en vänsterhand är helt enkelt inte möjligt; de passar inte lika bra. En liknande sak händer i naturen och kemin med kirala molekyler. För att en viss process ska fortskrida på ett specifikt sätt måste oftast en kiral molekyl passa tätt in i en viss del av en stor kiral miljö. Men precis som med handslag där du kan skaka med din högra eller vänstra hand, kan den kirala molekylen vänster- och högersidiga form passa in på två olika ställen och göra två olika reaktioner. I vissa fall har detta ingen betydande effekt, men i andra kan det få ett katastrofalt resultat. Av denna anledning är det viktigt att kunna framställa endast en form av en kiral molekyl i många aspekter av livet, för att säkerställa att den molekylen bara gör vad den är avsedd att göra och inget annat. Detta är vad som kallas asymmetrisk syntes och asymmetrisk hydrogenering är ett av dess många delområden. Den joniska formen av metallen iridium, som en del av en mer komplex struktur, har använts i framgångsrika hydrogeneringsreaktioner med många olika molekyler som substrat, förutom de som innehåller en aldehydgrupp. Från detta tomrum i litteraturen härrör huvudsyftet med detta arbete, och det är att presentera en metodik för att framställa kirala aldehyd-innehållande molekyler direkt eller indirekt genom en "maskering" av aldehyden med en tillfällig funktionell grupp som är lätt att installera och efteråt ta bort. Oxim-etrar är kända för att lätt bildas från sina motsvarande aldehyder och uppvisar god reaktivitet och selektivitet med vanliga iridiumkatalysatorer. Slutligen kan ozon appliceras för att regenerera aldehydfunktionen från oximeter-produkten.

a) Ursprunget till ordet kiral

b) I vissa fall luktar de två formerna av en kiral molekyl annorlunda

Figur A. Ursprunget till ordet kiral och ett exempel på de olika egenskaperna hos kirala föreningar.

^a Orden kiral och kiralitet kommer från det grekiska ordet för hand ($\chi\epsilon\iota\rho$) och de är besläktade med det faktum att kirala molekyler, ungefär som händer, har samma konstitution och anslutningsmöjligheter men är spegelbilder av varandra. Som en konsekvens kan de vänster- och högersidiga formerna av en sådan molekyl inte ömsesidigt överlagras (Fig. Aa). Ett sätt att märka skillnaderna mellan dessa två former av samma molekyl är i deras doft. Till exempel har (+)-karvon en mintig doft, medan (-)-karvon luktar mer som kummin (Fig. Ab).

List of Abbreviations

Table A. Abbreviations used in the following text.

Abbreviation	Full name
BAr _F ⁻	Tetrakis(3,5-bis(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)borate anion
BenzP*	1,2-Bis(<i>tert</i> -butylmethylphosphino)benzene
BINAP	2,2'-Bis(diphenylphosphino)-1,1'-binaphthyl
Bn	Benzyl
Bz	Benzoyl
cat	Catalyst
CG	Coordinating group
COD	Cyclooctadiene
conv.	Conversion
Cy	Cyclohexyl
DCM	Dichloromethane
DIOP	2,3- <i>O</i> -Isopropylidene-2,3-dihydroxy-1,4-bis(diphenylphosphino)butane
DIPAMP	1,2-Ethandiyldis[(2-methoxyphenyl)(phenyl)phosphine
DKR	Dynamic kinetic resolution
DMP	Dess-Martin periodinane
ee	Enantiomeric excess
FG	Functional group
L	Ligand
L-DOPA	L-3,4-Dihydroxyphenylalanine
NADH	Reduced nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide
NHC	N-Heterocyclic carbene
NMR	Nuclear magnetic resonance
<i>o</i> -Tol	<i>ortho</i> -Tolyl
OYE(2,3)	Old yellow enzyme
pyr	Pyridine
TangPhos	1- <i>tert</i> -Butyl-2-(1- <i>tert</i> -butylphospholan-2-yl)phospholane
Tf	Trifluoromethylsulfonyl
TFE	2,2,2-Trifluoroethanol
TOF	Turnover frequency
TON	Turnover number
TPPTS	Trisodium 3,3',3''-phosphanetriyltri(benzene-1-sulfonate)

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1. Introduction

1.1. Asymmetric synthesis and the role of asymmetric hydrogenation

Nature is perhaps the largest known chiral environment. The chemistry of life strongly relies on the ability of biological systems to be able to differentiate their left from their right hand on the molecular level, i.e., to recognize one enantiomer of a molecule from the other. Vital processes such as the ability to metabolize glucose, the synthesis of enzymes, and even the reactions they catalyze involve the use of chirality in some form. Additionally, sex pheromones used by insects (Fig. 1.1a) to attract a partner¹, or the ability of bacteria to evade the immune system of their host^{a,2}, are two examples of natural processes that heavily rely on the presence of specific enantiomers of a chiral molecule. Medicines like L-DOPA, (*S*)-ketoprofen or (*R*)-thalidomide^b (Fig. 1.1b-d) boast a lack of activity to serious health effects, if their opposite enantiomers are used, especially in the latter case.³ These are just a handful of examples that justify the necessity in developing highly efficient and reliable protocols for the selective synthesis of chiral compounds in a pure enantiomeric form.

a) The female Banded cucumber beetle (*Diabrotica balteata*) sex pheromone

b) L-DOPA

c) (*S*)-Ketoprofen

d) (*R*)-Thalidomide

e) Brucine

Figure 1.1. Structures of some important chiral motifs and compounds.

Asymmetric synthesis has come a long way since its inception in the late nineteenth and early twentieth century with Fischer's work on the chemistry of sugars⁴ and Marckwald's brucine-catalyzed (Fig. 1.1e) decarboxylation of 2-ethyl-2-methylmalonic acid to 2-methylbutiric acid proceeding with a small enantiomeric excess.⁵ It was not until the middle and end of the twentieth century that some of the most important tools for conducting asymmetric synthesis were developed. Perhaps the most prominent examples of this were Sharpless' asymmetric epoxidation and dihydroxylation reactions, and Knowles' and Noyori's breakthroughs in asymmetric hydrogenation which earned all of them the 2001 Nobel Prize in Chemistry.⁶

Today we can define several ways to approach the task of preparing chiral molecules. These include: resolution of a racemate, using a starting material from the chiral pool, or using a chiral auxiliary or a chiral ligand in an asymmetric induction (Scheme 1.1a). Although in principle, the latter approach can be performed either stoichiometrically or catalytically, the use of

^a Unlike eukaryotes which largely have L-amino acids, prokaryotic cells, i.e., bacteria, produce a wide range of D-amino acids like D-alanine and D-glutamic acid to protect their cell walls from external threats.²

^b Due to the *in vivo* racemization of the active (*R*)-thalidomide^{3a}, in the early 1960s this drug used to treat morning sickness in pregnant women became the reason for serious birth defects to their unborn fetuses.³

catalytic reactions with chiral ligands are one of the most appealing methods due to their simplicity, low catalyst loadings and generally high yields and enantioselectivities. Catalytic asymmetric hydrogenation fits this profile and in recent decades has proven itself to be an indispensable tool for installing chirality on a prochiral substrate with a high atom economy and excellent control over selectivity.

a) A breakdown of asymmetric synthesis

b) Knowles' and Horner's initial work, 1968

c) Monsanto's synthesis of L-DOPA developed by Knowles, 1975

Scheme 1.1. Approaches in conducting asymmetric synthesis and some examples of asymmetric hydrogenation reactions.

The development in terms of efficacy in asymmetric hydrogenation since the first work of Knowles^{a,6c} (Scheme 1.1b) has excelled from poor to excellent optical yields in a very short period of time as demonstrated with the synthesis of L-DOPA by the same author⁸ (Scheme 1.1c). Ligand design and catalyst development, of course, are the center point in the successful and rapid evolution in the field. Chiral bidentate ligands like the diphosphines: DIOP, DIPAMP, BINAP, and later TangPhos, BenzP* (Fig. 1.2) and others have played a crucial role in Rh- and Ru-catalyzed hydrogenations starting from more modest enantioselectivities and leading to very acceptable ones while at the same time broadening their substrate scope applicability.⁹

Figure 1.2. Structures of some chiral bidentate diphosphine ligands.

Though admirably useful, rhodium and ruthenium complexes have some limitations when it comes to hydrogenating isolated alkenes. In the 1990s Pfaltz introduced a chiral modification

^a Independently from Knowles at the same time Horner et al. reported similar findings.⁷

to Crabtree's catalyst¹⁰ ($[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\text{PCy}_3)(\text{pyr})]^+[\text{PF}_6]^-$) bearing a bidentate N,P-type ligand. He demonstrated its usefulness in reducing unfunctionalized alkenes with high enantioselectivity on a model substrate^{11a} (Scheme 1.2a) but also on a more practical example like a precursor to the vitamin E constituent γ -tocopherol^{11b} (Scheme 1.2b). Subsequent research done by the groups of Pfaltz, Burgess and Andersson further contributed to the development of iridium-catalyzed hydrogenations, and alongside with the design of new and efficient ligands, more unfunctionalized and even functionalized alkenes could be reduced in an asymmetric fashion (Scheme 1.2c).^{12,13} Iridium also proved useful for other functional groups like ketones and imines reducing them to their respected chiral alcohols¹⁴ and amines¹⁵ (Scheme 1.2d). This was accomplished with the help of chiral NHC,P-ligands which have shown promising results in terms of reducing polar multiple bonds like C=O or C=N.

Scheme 1.2. Examples of iridium-catalyzed asymmetric hydrogenation reactions using various ligand systems.

1.2. Details of iridium-catalyzed hydrogenation reactions

Iridium catalysts are ionic complexes and while enantioselectivities are largely dependent on the chiral ligand, the performance in terms of reactivity and turnover numbers are affected by the nature of the solvent and the counterion to the metal center. Iridium forms relatively stable catalytic intermediates, compared to rhodium for example, even allowing for their characterization by NMR.¹⁶ Because of this, weakly coordinating solvents such as DCM or toluene proved to be highly effective for fast iridium catalysis.¹⁷ One very notable drawback of iridium is its tendency to form H-bridged trimers, impeding any catalytic activity.¹⁸ This property is the most common mode for catalyst deactivation and early on, Pfaltz was able to overcome this obstacle by replacing the PF₆⁻ anion in the classical Crabtree-type catalyst with the practically non-coordinating and sterically bulky BARF⁻ anion. This change led to higher reactivity at lower catalyst loadings and subsequently became the norm in catalyst design (Scheme 1.3a).^{9,11a,16a,17}

a) Effect of the counterion on the reactivity

^a TOF = TON / t, [h⁻¹]

b) Mechanism of an alkene hydrogenation reaction with an Ir-N,P catalyst

Scheme 1.3. The effect of the counterion on the reactivity and an example of the mechanism of an iridium-catalyzed hydrogenation reaction.

In terms of the mechanism, Ir-catalyzed hydrogenations of alkenes with Ir-N,P catalysts are accepted to proceed through an Ir^{III}/Ir^V-catalytic cycle (Scheme 1.3b) as supported by various computational studies.^{16b,19} Prior to the main hydrogenation reaction, the Ir^I-precatalyst **i** undergoes oxidation to an active Ir^{III}-species which performs two consecutive hydrogenations transforming the COD ligand into cyclooctane. After replacement of the latter with a molecule of H₂ and a molecule of the olefinic substrate structure **ii** is formed from which the catalytic cycle begins. This structure is also suggested to be the resting state of catalyst, as reported by

Pfalts.^{16b} An oxidative addition of the coordinated H-H molecule proceeds simultaneously with a migratory insertion of a hydride into the C=C bond yielding intermediate **iv** via transition state **iii**. A reductive elimination with a hydrogen transfer completes the reaction giving structure **v**. The catalytic cycle is closed with the release of the final product and the regeneration of intermediate **ii**. It is widely accepted that the oxidative addition/migratory insertion between **ii** and **iv** is the rate- and, in some cases, the selectivity-determining step of the reaction.^{16a,19b,21a}

Based on the Ir^{III}/Ir^V-mechanism, a very useful mnemonic model for predicting the absolute configuration of the majorly formed enantiomer was developed and successfully applied by the Andersson group.²⁰ The model arranges the steric environment around the chiral ligand into four quadrants viewed from the incoming alkene substrate. The orientation of the substrate during the initial coordination to the catalyst is trans to the phosphorus atom and in such a way that minimizes the steric hindrance inside the catalyst-substrate complex. This leads to the ability to visualize which prochiral face of the C=C bond is preferred and, subsequently, which enantiomer of the product would be preferentially formed (Fig. 1.3).

Figure 1.3. A selectivity model for Ir-N,P-catalyzed hydrogenation reactions.

A discussion of iridium chemistry would be incomplete without mentioning convergency. The vast majority of asymmetric hydrogenation reactions are stereospecific; thus, the enantiomer of the product is dependent on the *E/Z*-geometry around the C=C bond. With some catalysts and substrates, on the other hand, a diastereomeric mixture of the starting material yields exclusively a single enantiomer of the product (Scheme 1.4a). This phenomenon is termed enantioconvergence and it is accepted to proceed through one of few ways: double bond isomerism; DKR; or hydrogenation through a shared catalytic intermediate, with the former two being the most common scenarios.^{21a} Chelation control that largely ignores steric interactions is also suggested to allow for convergency, preferentially with α -prochiral substrates having a functional group liable for coordination to the metal center (Scheme 1.4b).^{a,21a} In this case, an Ir^I/Ir^{III}-mechanism would be more appropriate since the chelated substrate would hinder the η^2 -coordination of the second H₂-molecule, impeding in this way the oxidative addition needed to generate the Ir^V-species.^{21c}

^a It is common in convergent chelation-controlled asymmetric hydrogenations for the opposite enantiomer, from the one predicted by the sterics-controlled quadrant model, to be formed. This mismatch in the predicted versus the observed absolute stereochemistry is one of the ways to detect a possible chelation control for the reaction.²¹

Substrate-wise, olefins are frequently synthesized as *E/Z*-mixtures. Thus, their use as substrates in asymmetric hydrogenations requires a separation step, which is both time-consuming and waste-generating. Therefore, the availability of reaction protocols that exhibit enantioconvergence offers a prime advantage over typically divergent ones.²¹ Lastly, iridium is not the only metal to allow for convergence. For example, rhodium and even nickel catalysts have also been reported to partake in this type of stereochemical outcome (Scheme 1.4c).²²

a) A representation of enantioconvergence

b) Enantioconvergence through chelation control

Regular selectivity model (sterics control)

(Z)-

(E)-

Chelation model

(Z)-

(E)-

c) Examples of enantioconvergent asymmetric hydrogenations

Scheme 1.4. A representation of enantioconvergence, chelation and examples of convergent asymmetric hydrogenations with different metal catalysts.

The beginning of this section dealt with increasing the reactivity of the Ir-N,P catalysts, but quite often the first attempt at hydrogenating a new substrate gives an unsatisfactory optical yield. The reason for this is that certain substrates require a degree of variation in the steric and electronic properties of the chiral ligand in order to achieve optimal enantioselection.²³ The way to tackle this issue in practice is to choose a well-performing chiral ligand backbone on

the substrate in question and modify certain structural features of it. Most often, modifications made to the substituents around the heterocycle and the phosphorus atom are adequate in achieving this objective and result in satisfactory enantiomeric excesses for a wide range of substrates of a common type (Scheme 1.5).²⁴

Scheme 1.5. Comparison between differently substituted chiral Ir-N,P catalysts.

1.3. Asymmetric hydrogenation of unsaturated aldehydes, oximes, and aims of this work

Beginning with its ability to efficiently hydrogenate unfunctionalized olefins, iridium catalysis has established itself as a reliable tool for the reduction of functionalized olefins, but it also allows for the transformation of carbonyls into chiral alcohols and imines into chiral amines, rivaling or even surpassing the capabilities of rhodium and ruthenium catalysis. The plethora of substrate classes that are susceptible to asymmetric hydrogenation by chiral iridium complexes is truly broad. Prochiral α,β -unsaturated ketones, carboxylic acids and their derivatives, phosphonates, sulfones, allylic alcohols, or dehydroamino acid derivatives are at best just a handful of the substrates that are most commonly reported in efficient iridium-catalyzed hydrogenation protocols.^{21c,25} Yet, one functional group is nearly all but forgotten amongst this common and standard substrate motif: the aldehyde (Scheme 1.6). The products of such hydrogenations: saturated chiral aldehydes, are frequently used in the perfume industry making them attractive targets in synthesis, especially at a time when the health effects associated with many fragrance molecules are being reevaluated.²⁶

Scheme 1.6. Some commonly reported functionalized olefins used as substrates in Ir-catalyzed asymmetric hydrogenation reactions.

a) Reducing unsaturated aldehydes with metal catalysts

b) Enantioselective reductions with enzymatic catalysts

Scheme 1.7. Examples of reactions known to reduce unsaturated aldehydes to saturated ones.

Reports for the racemic hydrogenation of α,β -unsaturated aldehydes display metals such as rhodium and palladium as effective catalysts for reducing the C=C bond and preserving the carbonyl function (Scheme 1.7a).²⁷ Enzyme-catalyzed asymmetric reductions, like the one reported by Faber, are shown to reduce unsaturated aldehydes enantioselectively with satisfying results (Scheme 1.7b).²⁸ However, metal-catalyzed enantioselective protocols are lacking for the hydrogenation of these types of prochiral substrates. That is why the aims of this current project are to investigate the challenges behind the reduction of unsaturated aldehydes and devise a strategy for transforming one such molecule into a saturated chiral aldehyde, with satisfying yields and selectivities.

Oximes are readily formed from aldehydes (Scheme 1.8a).²⁹ This presents an opportunity for their use as protecting groups for unsaturated aldehydes during asymmetric hydrogenation. Employing such a strategy dictates that a reliable method for subsequent deprotection is required, and usually this is performed in some kind of acidic media. For example, glyoxylic, or *o*-iodobenzoic acids are reported to yield an aldehyde product after oxime hydrolysis.³⁰ This approach is more appealing after installing a β -stereocenter in the oxime molecule but less so with an α -chiral product, due to the possibility of racemization around the chiral carbon. Cleavage of the C=N bond by ozone or (BnPPH₃)₂Cr₂O₇, on the other hand, are known to yield carbonyls from their respected oximes (Scheme 1.8b).^{31,32} These two approaches have the potential to circumvent the problem of racemization, and to allow for the deprotection of α -chiral oximes to their corresponding chiral aldehydes with retention of the chiral information.

a) Preparation of oximes and oxime ethers from aldehydes

b) Regenerating aldehydes from oximes

Scheme 1.8. Some methods used to install and remove an oxime functionality from a carbonyl compound.

2. Results and Discussion

The conversion of a reaction is used to quantify the amount of starting material transformed into the reaction products (Eq. 1). Asymmetric hydrogenation reactions quite often proceed cleanly and yield only one major product with the formation of little to no byproducts. Because it is dependent on catalyst loading, choice of solvent, temperature, and pressure, the conversion is commonly reported in screening trials as a direct measure of the reaction's efficiency and starting material reactivity. In this case, the conversion is also related to the yield of the product, thus hydrogenation reactions are initially optimized to proceed with full or high conversion before large-scale reactions are performed.^{21c}

$$\text{Equation 1.} \quad \text{conv.} = \frac{\sum_i(\text{product})_i}{(\text{starting material}) + \sum_i(\text{product})_i} 100, \quad [\%]$$

The enantiomeric excess of a chiral compound is related to the amounts of both enantiomers in the sample, and it is expressed with Eq. 2.

$$\text{Equation 2.} \quad \text{ee} = \frac{|R - S|}{R + S} 100, \quad [\%]$$

In the following text, which presents the results and discussion of this work, all chiral ligands used in the asymmetric hydrogenation reactions are represented with a corresponding bolded capital letter as shown in Fig. 2.1.

Figure 2.1. Chiral N,P-type ligands used in the herein report.

2.1. Direct hydrogenation of unsaturated aldehydes and the use of a protecting group

As a model substrate for direct hydrogenation, unsaturated aldehyde **1** was chosen. The compound is a typical α -prochiral functionalized olefin, representing a motif which is commonly used in asymmetric hydrogenation reactions. Three iridium catalysts were screened for the reactivity of **1** at different pressures, temperatures, and reaction times (Table 2.1). Toluene was chosen as the solvent to allow heating to higher temperatures. Conditions which included hydrogen pressures of 20 or 50 bar at room temperature did not produce conversions higher than 5%. Replacing the chiral catalyst with Crabtree's catalyst showed practically no reactivity (entry 6). Conditions wise, an increase in the reaction temperature to 40 or 60 °C showed minimal change, however, stronger heating to 80 °C gave a noticeable increase in conversion. Longer reaction times and an additive of benzamide (entry 10) allowed for full conversion of the starting material, though, product **c** was solely produced.

Table 2.1. Reactivity screening of the model substrate.

Entry	Ligand	Additive	Pressure	Temperature	Time	Conv.	Ratio (a:b:c:d)
1	A	-	20 bar	rt	2 h	< 5%	-
2	A	-	20 bar	rt	o.n.	< 5%	-
3	A	-	20 bar	60 °C	o.n.	<10%	-
4	B	-	20 bar	rt	o.n.	< 5%	-
5	B	-	20 bar	60 °C	o.n.	<10%	-
6	Crabtree	-	50 bar	rt	o.n.	< 1%	-
7	A	-	50 bar	80 °C	1 h	35%	1 : 5 : 8 : 0
8	A	-	50 bar	80 °C	o.n.	44%	1 : 20 : 14 : 0
9	A	BzNH ₂ ^a	50 bar	80 °C	1 h	20%	1 : 12 : 29 : 0
10	A	BzNH ₂ ^a	50 bar	80 °C	o.n.	>99%	only c (62% ee)
11	A	-	50 bar	rt	1 h	< 2%	-
12	A	-	50 bar	rt	5 h	2%	-
13	A	-	50 bar	40 °C	1 h	< 4%	-
14	A	-	50 bar	40 °C	5 h	98% ^b	1 : 5 : 60 : 0

^a The additive and catalyst are stirred at room temperature for 1h in toluene under a pillow of argon.

^b Unreproducible.

Coordination of the carbonyl group or the entire conjugated system in **1** to the iridium center forming a stable complex with no catalytic activity was suggested as a possible reason for the lack of reactivity at milder conditions. However, competition reactions using three different substrates, which normally possess high reactivity with the corresponding Ir-catalyst, largely refuted this hypothesis (Scheme 2.1a). The idea that the aldehyde group hinders the reactivity was further disproven with the successful hydrogenation of (*R*)-citronellal proceeding to full conversion and yielding (*R*)-dihydrocitronellal as the only product of the reaction (Scheme 2.1b).

a) Competition reactions between the model unsaturated aldehyde and other substrates

b) Asymmetric hydrogenation of (*R*)-citronellal

Scheme 2.1. Competition reactions and hydrogenation of citronellal.

It is well known that olefin reactivity depends on the number of substituents around the C=C bond, and it follows the general reactivity order of tetra- < tri- < disubstituted. Thus, the terminal analogue of **1** – compound **t1**, which is a disubstituted olefin, was subjected to asymmetric hydrogenation. Immediately a stark difference was seen in terms of its reactivity, giving full conversion in all cases (Table 2.2). The products of the reaction, however, are again multiple and tend to similarly favor the formation of the fully saturated alcohol **c** at higher temperatures (entries 1-4). Interestingly, at lower temperatures, **t1** yields carboxylic acid **d** as the major product of the reaction, likely the result of a disproportionation (entries 5-8). In these cases, no allylic alcohol was identified in the product mixture, something that is very prevalent in the hydrogenations of substrate **1** (Table 2.1, entries 7-9, 14).

The direct asymmetric hydrogenation of unsaturated aldehydes has proven challenging, as demonstrated with compound **1**. Aldehyde reactivity is minimal at lower temperatures, and supplying the reaction with high hydrogen pressures and sufficient heating is a requirement for achieving conversion of the starting material. Additionally, the desired saturated aldehyde product **a** is produced in low or trace amounts, even with shorter reaction times. The prevalence of the two alcohol products **b** and **c** implies that the catalyst prefers to hydrogenate the carbonyl group, ignoring the olefin until a more reactive allylic alcohol is formed *in situ* (product **b**). Competition experiments and employing a non-conjugated enal as the substrate have refuted catalyst inhibition by the substrate, and rather point towards a strong deactivating effect of the carbonyl group over the trisubstituted double bond. With this in mind, a strategy involving the use of a protecting group in place of the carbonyl was suggested to circumvent the low reactivity of this type of olefin.

Table 2.2. Asymmetric hydrogenation of a prochiral terminal olefin with an aldehyde group.

Entry	Additive	Pressure	Temperature	Time	Conv.	Ratio (a:b:c:d)
1	-	50 bar	80 °C	1 h	>99%	1 : 0 : 2 : 4
2	-	50 bar	80 °C	o.n.	>99%	1 : 0 : 2 : 0
3	BzNH ₂ ^a	50 bar	80 °C	1 h	>99%	1 : 0 : 12 : 0
4	BzNH ₂ ^a	50 bar	80 °C	o.n.	>99%	only c (26% ee)
5	-	50 bar	rt	1 h	>99%	1 : 0 : 1 : 15 ^b
6	-	50 bar	rt	5 h	>99%	1 : 0 : 3 : 22
7	-	50 bar	40 °C	1 h	>99%	1 : 0 : 4 : 20
8	-	50 bar	40 °C	5 h	>99%	1 : 0 : 6 : 13

^a The additive and catalyst are stirred at room temperature for 1h in toluene under a pillow of argon.

^b Product **d** is confirmed both by ¹H and ¹³C NMR.

To investigate a protecting group strategy as a relay towards chiral aldehydes, a number of protected versions of compound **1** were synthesized, consisting mainly of oxime derivatives (Scheme 2.2). In addition, a dioxolane protecting group is considered (compound **1ae**) in light of its widespread use in carbonyl protections, but also, the potential for high reactivity and selectivity during hydrogenation due to its structural similarity to allylic alcohols and ethers. The initial trial reactions (Table 2.3) pointed out that the free oxime **1ad** and its *O*-acylated analogue **1adAc** were completely unreactive towards hydrogenation with Ir-N,P catalysts (entries 5-6). Competition reactions with *trans*- α -methylstilbene suggest that these substrates completely poison the Ir-catalyst, leading to a lack of conversion even for the stilbene. Compound **1ae** showed moderate to satisfactory conversion and optical yields, achieving 97% ee as the highest value obtained (entry 7). The use of an oxime ether sparked potential, with **1a** producing a product with 99% ee, even on the initial trial study (entry 1). From there three additional oxime ethers: **1aa**, **1ab** and **1ac**, were tested, however **1a** proved the most attractive.

^a The reaction gave multiple unknown byproducts, which were difficult to separate.

Scheme 2.2. Differently protected versions of compound **1**.

Table 2.3. Initial trial reactions with protected versions of compound **1**.

Entry	Substrate	PG	Conv.	ee
1	1a	CH=NOMe	64%	99%
4	1ac	CH=NOBn	36%	-
5	1ad	CH=NOH	no reaction	-
6	1adAc	CH=NOAc	no reaction	-
7 ^a	1ae	CH(1,3-dioxolane)	66%	97%

^a The reaction conditions are 40 bar of hydrogen pressure and a temperature of 60 °C with 10 mol% of K₂CO₃ as an additive. This was the highest ee achieved for compound **1ae**.

Table 2.4. Reactivity and selectivity screening of substrate **1ae**.

Entry	Ligand	Additive	Pressure	Temperature	Conv.	ee	Ratio (a:b:c:d)
1	A	-	40 bar	60 °C	<99%	91%	only a
2	A	K ₂ CO ₃ (10 mol%)	40 bar	60 °C	66%	97%	only a
3	B	-	40 bar	60 °C	<99%	73%	only a
4	B	K ₂ CO ₃ (10 mol%)	40 bar	60 °C	89%	85%	only a
5	B	-	40 bar	rt	<99%	91%	20 : 1 : 0 : 0
6	B	K ₂ CO ₃ (10 mol%)	40 bar	rt	94%	85%	20 : 1 : 0 : 0
7	A	K ₂ CO ₃ (5 mol%)	10 bar	rt	97%	-	12 : 1 : 0 : 0
8	A	-	10 bar	rt	>99%	-	8 : 1 : 0 : 0
9	A	-	10 bar	40 °C	<99%	-	12 : 1 : 0 : 4
10	C	-	40 bar	60 °C	<99%	95%	only a
11	A	K ₂ CO ₃ (4 mol%)	40 bar	60 °C	<99%	95%	only a
12	C	K ₂ CO ₃ (4 mol%)	40 bar	60 °C	<99%	96%	only a

A screening of catalysts and conditions revealed that substrate **1ae** possesses high reactivity, even with mild conditions (Table 2.4). Optical yields were moderate, tending to decrease with an increase in temperature. An additive of K₂CO₃ slightly improved the enantiomeric excess, though, larger loadings tend to decrease the conversion. A 4 mol% K₂CO₃ loading had a small positive effect on improving the optical yield without affecting the conversion (entries 11-12). Milder conditions, including lower hydrogen pressures and a lack of heating, however, allowed for partial deprotection of **1ae** to aldehyde **1** (entries 5-9). Thus, higher pressures with heating are suggested optimal for this substrate in order to conserve the dioxolane moiety. Nevertheless, the difficulty in achieving efficient hydrogenation, coupled with the challenging synthesis of **1ae**, prompted the development of an oxime ether-based relay hydrogenation towards the targeted chiral aldehydes. In addition, synthesis of the β-methyl version of **1ae** was attempted, which proved even more challenging, due to partial deprotection proceeding upon storage.

2.2. Oxime ethers: reaction optimization

Compound **1a** served as the main model substrate for developing the oxime ether asymmetric hydrogenation. In addition, a substrate with only aliphatic substituents around the double bond **3a** was synthesized, due to the deficit of aliphatic substrates in hydrogenation reactions. Beta-methyl versions of the two model compounds **2a** and **4a** were also synthesized to examine the efficiency of the reaction with a different substituent pattern around the olefin (Scheme 2.3).

Scheme 2.3. Synthesized model substrates for the asymmetric hydrogenation of oxime ethers.

A number of catalysts were screened with substrate **1a** using DCM as the solvent (Table 2.5). Those using ligands **A** and **B** are identified as performing the best in terms of reactivity and selectivity, however, the change in the solvent showed a decrease in reactivity. Thus, toluene was deemed best, and another screening carried out (Table 2.6) identified the most optimal conditions for the hydrogenation of **1a** to be a catalyst loading of 1 mol%, 10 bar of hydrogen pressure, heating to 40 °C, and a reaction time of around 16 hours (overnight). These conditions were subsequently employed as standard for the hydrogenation of oxime ethers.

Table 2.5. Catalyst screening for substrate **1a**.

Table 2.6. Conditions screening for substrate **1a**.

Entry	Ligand	cat. loading	Pressure	Temperature	Conv.	ee
1	A	1 mol%	15 bar	rt	60%	99%
2	A	1 mol%	20 bar	rt	53%	99%
3	A	1 mol%	50 bar	rt	55%	99%
4	A	1 mol%	20 bar	60 °C	99%	99%
5	A	1 mol%	10 bar	40 °C	99%	>99%
6	A	0.5 mol%	10 bar	40 °C	95%	>99%
7	B	1 mol%	10 bar	rt	95%	>99%
8	B	1 mol%	10 bar	40 °C	99%	>99%

Table 2.7. Hydrogenation of different oxime ethers with the standard reaction conditions.

1a A: 99% conv., >99% ee

1aa A: 99% conv., >99% ee

1ab A: 47% conv. (1 mol%)
74% conv. (2 mol%)
81% conv. (3 mol%)^a

1ac A: 96% conv. (1 mol%)
>99% conv. (2 mol%)
91% ee (on alcohol)

3a A: 4% conv.
D: 13% conv., 79% ee
G: 88% conv., 33% ee
H: 32% conv., 93% ee

^a The reaction is ran at a temperature of 60 °C. This is the highest conv. achieved for compound **1ab**.

A number of oxime ethers bearing different substituents on the oxime oxygen were synthesized (Scheme 2.2) and subjected to asymmetric hydrogenation with the standard conditions serving as a starting point (Table 2.7). Compound **1aa** showed identical behavior to **1a**, while **1ab** and

1ac required higher catalyst loadings, the former even heating, in order to increase the reactivity. Furthermore, challenges in identifying an analytical method for ee analysis made the *t*-Bu and Bn oxime ethers undesirable. While the performance of the Et oxime ether is the same as the Me, the latter was identified to be better at serving in a protecting group, thanks to its smaller molecular weight, reducing the loss in the overall atom economy associated with the protection and deprotection steps. Substrate **3a** showed extremely low reactivity with ligand **A**. A screening was carried out, and an imidazole-type backbone was chosen for further screening (Table 2.7). Ligands **B** and **K** show the best selectivity and reactivity for **3a** (Table 2.8), though, the optical yield never reached more than 95%. A small solvent screening with the aim to identify a better performing solvent was conducted, however, toluene remained the best option, giving the highest conversion and enantiomeric excess (Scheme 2.4).

Table 2.8. Catalyst screening for substrate **3a**.

^a These are the highest ee values obtained for compound **3b**, and they have shown difficult to reproduce. Optical yields of 90 to 91% are most commonly obtained.

Scheme 2.4. Solvent screening for substrate **3a**.

As mentioned in the introduction, isolating a β -chiral aldehyde would eliminate the probability of racemization during and after the oxime deprotection, while at the same time allowing for a wider substrate scope to be compatible with the reaction protocol, but also more deprotection methods to be employed, including ones with acidic conditions. Compound **2a**, thus, was subjected to a catalyst and conditions screening (Table 2.9). The standard hydrogenating conditions proved unsatisfactory, however, an increase in catalyst loading, hydrogen pressure, and reaction temperature showed a gradual increase in conversion, achieving moderate

enantioselectivity. Though the reactivity proved difficult to reproduce and maintain, the optical yield remained stable giving the highest values of 91-92% ee (entries 6, 8) at 50 bar of pressure and a temperature of 60 °C with ligand **B**.

Compound **3a**, which was isolated as a 2:1 *E/Z* mixture around the C=N bond, similarly showed limited reactivity, not even reaching 90% conv. (Table 2.10). Optical yields were also lower and difficult to maintain, though the conditions used are milder compared to the ones for **2a**. A lack of convergency at the C=N bond is suggested to account for the lower and varying ee values. A careful chromatographic separation of the starting material carried out yielded a 4:1 and a 2:3 *1E/1Z* mixture of **2a**. The diastereomeric mixtures were subsequently hydrogenated to yield products having a 54% difference in ee between the two (Scheme 2.5); furthermore, a reverse in the elution order for the major enantiomer was noticed during the analysis. These observations align with the presumption for stereodivergence (stereospecificity) around the oxime double bond. The difference in conversion, on the other hand, might suggest that the Ir-center prefers to coordinate to the oxygen atom from the methoxy group during hydrogenation, rather than the oxime nitrogen, or it does not coordinate at all as expected, form a β -prochiral olefin bearing a functional group liable for chelation; however, further studies are required in order to confirm these observations.

Table 2.9. Catalyst and conditions screening for substrate **2a**.

2a $\xrightarrow[\text{H}_2, \text{Toluene, o.n.}]{[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})\text{L}]\text{BAR}_f}$ **2b**

A

B

G

J

K

M

M

Entry	Ligand	cat. loading	Pressure	Temperature	Conv.	ee
1	A	1 mol%	20 bar	rt	no conv.	-
2	A	1 mol%	20 bar	60 °C	no conv.	-
3	A	2 mol%	80 bar	80 °C	13%	84%
4	B	1 mol%	20 bar	60 °C	no conv.	-
5	B	2 mol%	40 bar	80 °C	27%	84%
6	B	2 mol%	50 bar	60 °C	28%	92%
7	B	2 mol%	80 bar	80 °C	73%	87%
8	B	3 mol%	50 bar	60 °C	22%	91%
9	B	1 mol%	100 bar	100 °C	50%	87%
10	G	1 mol%	80 bar	80 °C	3%	-
11	J	4 mol%	80 bar	80 °C	9%	88%
12	K	4 mol%	80 bar	80 °C	30%	84%
13	M	2 mol%	20 bar	60 °C	2%	-
14	M	2 mol%	40 bar	60 °C	2%	-

Table 2.10. Catalyst and conditions screening for substrate **3a**.

Entry	Ligand	cat. loading	Pressure	Temperature	Conv.	ee
1	A	2 mol%	20 bar	60 °C	63%	79%
2	A	2 mol%	40 bar	60 °C	87%	50%
3	B	2 mol%	20 bar	60 °C	53%	85%
4	B	5 mol%	40 bar	60 °C	73%	89% ^a
5	B	3 mol%	50 bar	60 °C	58%	82%
6	M	2 mol%	20 bar	60 °C	5%	-
7	M	2 mol%	40 bar	60 °C	5%	-

^a This is the highest ee value obtained for compound **4b**, and it has shown difficult to reproduce. An optical yield of 60% is most commonly obtained. Longer reaction times did not significantly improve the conversion of the starting material.

Scheme 2.5. Oxime convergency trial reactions for substrate **3a**.

Oxime ethers, bearing α -prochiral carbons, have proved themselves easier to hydrogenate using mild conditions to achieve perfect reactivity and selectivity. Their β -substituted counterparts present major difficulties, however, not allowing high conversions to be achieved with harsher conditions, even with longer reaction times. It is established that β -prochiral olefins do not display enantioconvergence when a chelating functional group is present.²¹ This points towards use of the Ir^{III}/Ir^V-mechanism, in which steric interactions between the chiral ligand and substrate are the dominating factor that determines the enantioselectivity. It is also expected, with this kind of mechanism, that a larger energy barrier exists, which, as a result, gives rise to lower reactivity. The experiments carried out with two different diastereomeric mixtures of one of the two β -prochiral oxime ethers, though modestly with room for further investigation, pointed towards a lack of chelation, or chelation with the less desirable site on the oxime functionality – the oxygen atom. Extrapolating this data to the α -substrates, a chelating mechanism, likely through the oxime nitrogen atom, would be expected to occur with all of its preceding consequences like the presence of enantioconvergence, as discussed earlier in the introduction.

2.3. Oxime ethers: substrate scope and deprotection

Following the reaction optimization, which yielded the most optimal conditions for oxime hydrogenations and revealed the oxime methyl ether as the most attractive enal protection, several novel oxime ether substrates were synthesized to serve as substrates for Ir-catalyzed asymmetric hydrogenation (Table 2.11).

Table 2.11. Synthesized novel oxime ether substrates for asymmetric hydrogenation.

$$\text{R}^1\text{-CH=C(CH}_3\text{)-CHO} \xrightarrow[\text{EtOH, H}_2\text{O, 80 }^\circ\text{C, o.n.}]{\text{H}_2\text{NOMe.HCl, NaOAc}} \text{R}^1\text{-CH=C(CH}_3\text{)-CH=N-OMe}$$

5-14 **5a-14a**

Entry	Starting material aldehyde	Oxime ether substrate	Yield
1	5a	59%	
2	6a	88%	
3	7a	95%	
4	8a	95%	
5	9a	90%	
6	10a	71%	
7	11a	72%	
8	12a	41%	
9	13a	41%	
10	E-14a	95%	
11	Z-14a	96%	

The synthesized substrates display examples of olefins containing aromatic and aliphatic; only aliphatic; and even only aromatic substituents around the double bond. On some of the aromatic substrates, functional groups having diverse electronic effects, influencing both the aromatic ring and the olefin, are present.

All of the synthesized oxime ethers (**5a-14a**) were thus subjected to asymmetric hydrogenation using the identified standard reaction conditions, employing ligands **A** or **B**, as the two most effective ones (Table 2.12). The need for higher catalyst loading immediately came forward for the majority of the substrates, with only **10a** requiring 1 mol% in order to achieve full conversion to **10b**, while others required 3-6 mol%. Optical yields are excellent with two exceptions. For **9b**, an extensive screening for a racemate resolution method was conducted, however, the compound proved impossible to resolve using various HPLC, SFC, or GC conditions. It also proved difficult to deprotect via ozonolysis, which hindered the ee analysis on the deprotected aldehyde or corresponding alcohol, for which resolution was not an issue. Product **13b**, which contains a cyclohexyl substituent, did not exceed 34% ee, even when different ligands were employed. The low ee values, on the other hand, are unsurprising considering that similar substrates bearing functional groups other than an oxime also tend to give a lower ee than expected. It is possible that the conformation or size of the Cy-ring has an effect on the enantioselectivity, perhaps causing unfavorable steric interactions with the ligand.

Table 2.12. Substrate scope for the oxime ether asymmetric hydrogenation.

^a This is the highest ee value obtained for compound **10b**, and it is often reproducible. However, the optical yields tend to fall between 95 and 99% depending on the purity of the substrate and catalyst.

The deprotection to yield chiral aldehydes is one of the central components for the usefulness of this work. As mentioned, α -chiral aldehydes possess an ability for racemization, if subjected to acidic or basic conditions. The ozonolytic cleavage of the oxime moiety avoids the use of strong acids and bases, thus allowing the protecting group to be removed with retention of the installed chirality from the hydrogenation step. The literature^{31,32} does not evade to mention that transforming a saturated oxime into a saturated aldehyde is indeed challenging. Nevertheless, a conditions screening, using **1b** as the model substrate, was conducted (Table 2.13) which showed methanol as the more effective solvent and dimethyl sulfide as the preferred quenching agent for obtaining the aldehyde product. Using no quenching agent led to no conversion. After multiple trial reactions, it was concluded that a brief bubbling of ozone and nitrogen afterwards is required, especially on smaller scales, to achieve full conversion without the formation of byproducts. The use of an ice bath was also found to be beneficial.

Partial racemization preceded, thus a deprotection using an alternative mild reaction was considered, which used $(\text{BnPPH}_3)_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ in boiling acetonitrile (entry 4), however, the reaction gave no conversion even after 1 hour of refluxing. NaBH_4 was employed as the quenching agent (entry 5), and **1cOH** was obtained with full retention of chirality, excluding that the ozonolysis has an affect on the chital center. Further screening identified that the work-up procedure is responsible for the partial racemization. Analysis of the ee using the crude product aldehyde showed almost perfect retention of chirality (entry 6). With this in mind, it is not suggested that silica gel or alumina chromatography is used in the work-up or purification of α -chiral aldehydes, due to the risk of partial racemization. Since the presented herein molecules are of small molecular weights, and are liquids, distillation is suggested to be used as the purification method, which is also more desirable than chromatography on a larger scale.

Table 2.13. Conditions screening for the ozonolytic deprotection.

Entry	Substrate	Initial ee	Reagent	Product	Conv.	Yield	ee
1 ^a		>99%	O ₃ , Me ₂ S DCM		98%	93%	66%
2 ^a		>99%	O ₃ , Me ₂ S MeOH		99%	95%	87%
3 ^a		>99%	O ₃ , Zn MeOH		99%	87%	6%
4 ^a		>99%	O ₃ , NaBH ₄ MeOH		94%	-	>99%
5 ^b		>99%	$(\text{BnPPH}_3)_2^-$ Cr_2O_7^2- , MeCN		no conv.	-	-
6 ^c		>99%	O ₃ , Me ₂ S MeOH		99%	89%	98%

^a Freshly generated ozone is bubbled through a solution of the substrate at 0 °C, followed by nitrogen degassing and addition of the quenching agent. The reaction is then stirred at room temperature and afterwards the crude product is purified by filtering through a plug of silica gel, neutral or basic alumina (eluent 1:1 pentane/diethyl ether). ^b To a solution of the oxidant a solution of the substrate is added and the reaction is stirred at 80 °C. ^c The ee was measured on the crude product without any purification.

A number of chiral oxime ethers were deprotected using the identified ozonolysis conditions (Table 3.14). The reaction proceeds with full conversion using the methyl oxime ethers, giving moderate yields and retention in chirality. Additionally, **1bc** is deprotected to its corresponding

chiral alcohol (entry 2), in order to reveal an optical yield of 91%, which is also assigned to its chiral benzyl oxime ether. A similar assessment of ee for **1bb** failed, giving only byproducts, an observation similar to **9b**.

Table 3.14. Ozonolytic deprotection of some chiral oxime ethers.

Entry	Substrate	Initial ee	Product	Conv.	Yield	ee
1 ^a		>99%		99% (Me ₂ S)	89%	98% (87%)
2 ^a		-		80% (NaBH ₄)	-	91%
3 ^a		91%		99% (Me ₂ S)	67%	91% (86%)
4 ^a		95%		99% (Me ₂ S)	88%	95% (89%)
5 ^a		98%		99% (Me ₂ S)	91%	97% (86%)

^a Freshly generated ozone is bubbled through a solution of the substrate at 0 °C for 60 seconds, followed by nitrogen degassing and addition of the quenching agent. The reaction is then stirred at room temperature for 30 minutes. The ee is determined on the crude product for all entries except for entry 2; In parentheses are the optical yields obtained after purification.

The two substrates **E-14a** and **Z-14a** (Scheme 2.11), after hydrogenation and deprotection would give the fragrance compound lilial **14c**. Which enantiomer is obtained based on the C=C bond geometry, however, would help to uncover a key insight into the mechanism through which the reaction proceeds. Their individual hydrogenations, both optimized to use ligand **B**, give a high ee (Table 2.12) and the elution order of the major enantiomer for both products **E-14b** and **Z-14b** was the same. The conversion for the *Z*-form is lower compared to the *E*-, which is expected. A combined reaction using a 1:1 mixture of the *E*- and *Z*-forms with the same reaction conditions similarly produced a highly enantioenriched product with the same major enantiomer as the individual reactions (Scheme 2.6a).

These observations pointed towards the presence of enantioconvergence, which favors the formation of one enantiomer exclusively, regardless of the double bond geometry. With this, a chelating mechanism is supported and postulated (Scheme 2.6b), which is further backed by the formation of the (*S*)-enantiomer of lilial – the opposite to the one predicted from the sterics controlled quadrant model applicable to ligand **B** (Scheme 2.6c).

The absolute stereochemistry of **14c** is assigned by comparing the sign of the obtained optical rotation with those of its corresponding enantiomers. The (*S*)- corresponds to the (+) sign, while the (*R*)- corresponds to the (-) sign.³³ Furthermore, it is known that (*R*)-lilial possesses a strong floral scent, while the (*S*)-form has little to no aroma. The isolated crude, though smelling of traced amounts of dimethyl sulfide, did not hint at any floral scent, nor did the purified compound (still having 86% enantiomeric purity). It is thus accepted, that the obtained absolute configuration using ligand **B** is the (*S*)-configuration and this finding was subsequently extrapolated to the entire oxime ether substrate scope.

a) Combined reaction using substrates E-14a and Z-14a

b) A postulated chelating mechanism

c) Selectivity determination using the quadrant models

Scheme 2.6. Convergence test reaction, postulated chelating mechanism, and selectivity predictions using the quadrant models.

Conclusions

In summary, the direct hydrogenation of unsaturated aldehydes with iridium N,P-chiral catalysts pointed towards a substantial deactivating effect of the aldehyde group on the double bond, leading to the preferential hydrogenation of the former when harsh conditions are employed. A protecting group approach was conceived, for which a number of novel protected substrates were synthesized and subjected to asymmetric hydrogenation. The methyl oxime ether functionality was identified as the most optimal protecting group for α,β -unsaturated aldehydes, giving excellent conversion and optical yields with optimized reaction conditions.

It was found that β -prochiral oxime ethers are far more challenging to hydrogenate, compared to their α -prochiral versions, likely due to the use of a different mechanism. A substrate scope of a number of novel oxime ether derivatives was synthesized and successfully hydrogenated, demonstrating the utility of the reaction. The demand for heating, and moderate pressures, but also higher catalyst loadings, demonstrated a level of difficulty for these types of substrates, which likely is rooted to the structural and electronic similarity to their corresponding aldehydes.

A fast deprotection method using ozone was optimized and used on several substrates to yield the desired chiral aldehydes with retention of the preinstalled chirality. Nevertheless, care should be taken during the deprotection and handling of the chiral aldehydes, due to the preceding risk of their effortless partial racemization. It was found that the hydrogenation of oxime ethers is convergent in terms of the C=C bond geometry, whereas a stereospecific outcome was suggested in terms of the C=N bond geometry. Finally, a three-step protocol using unsaturated prochiral aldehydes to yield their corresponding saturated chiral counterparts was developed, which circumvents the chemoselectivity towards the more reactive aldehyde group in these conjugated systems during hydrogenating conditions. It also avoids the use of stoichiometric oxidants and reductants to generate an aldehyde group from a chiral alcohol or chiral ester, respectively.

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Last two paragraphs translated to Bulgarian:

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Supporting Information

General information

The reported herein NMR spectra are obtained in a d^1 -chloroform solution on a *Bruker Avance Neo 400* spectrometer with a frequency of 400 MHz for ^1H , 377 MHz for ^{19}F , and 101 MHz for ^{13}C NMR spectra, unless stated otherwise. The chemical shifts are reported in ppm (δ) and referenced internally to the residual solvent signals. The enantiomeric excess is determined on an *Agilent 8860 GC* system or an *Agilent 1260 Infinity LCMS/SFC* system using an appropriate chiral column and eluent system. All specific rotations are measured on a *Rudolph Research Analytical Autopol IV* polarimeter ($c = [\text{g}/100\text{mL}]$, $l = 100$ mm). The molecular masses are obtained using a *Bruker Daltonics micrOTOF* spectrometer. Column chromatography and silica plugs are performed using *Silica Gel 60*, 40 – 63 μm as a stationary phase. Alumina plugs are performed using *Aluminium Oxide 90 Active Basic*, 63 – 200 μm or *Aluminiumoxid Aktiv Neutral, Merck*. Prior to use the DCM is distilled from CaH_2 , the diethyl ether and toluene are distilled from sodium and benzophenone, both under a nitrogen atmosphere. All other solvents and reagents used are purchased from local suppliers or prepared by following a reported procedure. The hydrogenation reactions are carried out in a *Parr 5000* multi reactor system. The ozone is generated using a *Pilodist* ozone generator. Finally, all the yields are reported on the isolated product after purification or after work-up, if used as a crude. Reaction conversions are measured based on the signal integrations in the ^1H NMR spectrum of the crude product.

Experimental section

General procedure I. Synthesis of α,β -unsaturated aldehydes

In a predried round-bottom flask a 60% sodium hydride dispersion (1.2 equiv.) is suspended in dry diethyl ether (30 mL) and placed in an ice bath under a nitrogen atmosphere. To this a suitable phosphoryl ester (1.2 equiv.) is added dropwise and the mixture is stirred at 0°C for 30 min. Afterwards, an ether solution of the appropriate carbonyl compound (1.0 equiv.) is added dropwise. The reaction mixture is allowed to warm up to room temperature and stirred overnight. After completion, indicated by TLC, the reaction is quenched with diluted aqueous NH_4Cl solution (20 mL) and the product is extracted with DCM. After drying and evaporation the crude product is purified by gravitational chromatography (eluent 200:1-100:1 pentane/diethyl ether) to yield the (*E*)- α,β -unsaturated ester.^{34a}

In a predried round-bottom flask LiAlH_4 (1.0 equiv.) is dissolved in dry diethyl ether (20 mL) and placed in an ice bath under a nitrogen atmosphere. To this an ether solution of the appropriate α,β -unsaturated ester (1.0 equiv.) is added dropwise, and the reaction is stirred at 0°C for 1 h. After completion, indicated by TLC, the reaction is quenched with saturated Na_2SO_4 solution (3-5 mL) and stirred until a white precipitate is formed. The quenched reaction mixture is filtered through celite and dried. Evaporating the solvent yields the desired allylic alcohol which is used in the next step without further purification.^{34b}

In a predried round-bottom flask DMP (1.2 equiv.) is suspended in dry DCM (20 mL) and placed under a nitrogen atmosphere. To this the appropriate allylic alcohol (1.0 equiv.) is added dropwise and the reaction is stirred at room temperature overnight. After completion, indicated by TLC, the reaction mixture is filtered through celite. The crude product is absorbed on silica gel and purified by flash chromatography (eluent 40:1-20:1 pentane/diethyl ether) to yield the desired α,β -unsaturated aldehyde.^{34c}

General procedure II. Synthesis of oxime ethers

A round-bottom flask is charged with the appropriate unsaturated aldehyde (1.0 equiv.), *O*-substituted-hydroxylamine hydrochloride (2.7 equiv.), sodium acetate (4.4 equiv.) and a 2:1 ethanol-water mixture (20 mL). A reflux condenser is connected, and the reaction is stirred at 80 °C overnight. After completion, indicated by TLC, to the cooled reaction mixture brine (10 mL) is added and the product is extracted with diethyl ether. After drying and evaporation the crude product is purified by flash chromatography (eluent 120:1-60:1 pentane/diethyl ether) to yield the corresponding α,β -unsaturated oxime ether as predominantly the 1*E*-diastereoisomer or, where stated, as an inseparable mixture of diastereoisomers around the C=N bond.

(*E*)-2-Methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde *O*-methyl oxime (1a)

Prepared from (*E*)-2-methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde (0.700 g, 4.79 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *O*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.078 g, 12.93 mmol, 2.7 equiv.). The spectroscopic data is in accordance with the literature; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.84 (d, *J* = 0.7 Hz, 1H), 7.39 – 7.27 (m, 5H), 6.63 (s, 1H), 3.93 (s, 3H), 2.12 (d, *J* = 1.4 Hz, 3H).³⁵

(*E*)-2-Methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde *O*-ethyl oxime (1aa)

Prepared from (*E*)-2-methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde (0.400 g, 2.74 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *O*-ethylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.721 g, 7.39 mmol, 2.7 equiv.); Eluent 60:1 pentane/diethyl ether. A colorless oil is obtained (0.482 g, 2.55 mmol, 93% yield). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.75 (d, *J* = 0.6 Hz, 1H), 7.28 – 7.14 (m, 5H), 6.52 (s, 1H), 4.11 – 4.05 (m, 2H), 2.02 (d, *J* = 1.3 Hz, 3H), 1.25 – 1.17 (m, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 153.60, 136.80, 135.87, 132.59, 129.44, 128.43, 127.55, 69.74, 14.72, 13.32. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₂H₁₅NO [M+Na]⁺ 212.1046, found 212.1039.

(*E*)-2-Methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde *O*-(*tert*-butyl) oxime (1ab)

Prepared from (*E*)-2-methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde (0.400 g, 2.74 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *O*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.928 g, 7.39 mmol, 2.7 equiv.); Eluent 60:1

pentane/diethyl ether. A colorless oil is obtained (0.535 g, 2.47 mmol, 90% yield). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.72 (d, $J = 0.6$ Hz, 1H), 7.28 – 7.14 (m, 5H), 6.49 (s, 1H), 2.03 (d, $J = 1.3$ Hz, 3H), 1.24 (s, 9H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 152.39, 137.05, 134.89, 133.39, 129.39, 128.39, 127.34, 78.99, 27.68, 13.35. HRMS-TOF calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 240.1359, found 240.1350.

(2E)-2-Methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde O-benzyl oxime (1ac)

Prepared from (*E*)-2-methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde (0.400 g, 2.74 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *O*-benzylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.180 g, 7.39 mmol, 2.7 equiv.); Eluent 60:1 pentane/diethyl ether. A colorless oil is obtained (0.681 g, 2.71 mmol, 99% yield). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.82 (d, $J = 0.6$ Hz, 1H), 7.36 – 7.13 (m, 10H), 6.53 (s, 1H), 5.07 (s, 2H), 2.02 (d, $J = 1.3$ Hz, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 154.29, 137.74, 136.71, 136.32, 132.43, 129.44, 128.56, 128.54, 128.44, 128.05, 127.62, 13.32. HRMS-TOF calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 274.1202, found 274.1212.

(2E)-3-Methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde O-methyl oxime (2a)

Prepared from (*E*)-3-methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde (0.600 g, 4.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *O*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.925 g, 11.08 mmol, 2.7 equiv.); Eluent 60:1 pentane/diethyl ether. A slowly crystallizing oil is obtained (0.696 g, 3.98 mmol, 97% yield). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.19 (d, $J = 10.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.52 – 7.45 (m, 2H), 7.40 – 7.28 (m, 3H), 6.53 (dq, $J = 10.4, 1.3$ Hz, 1H), 3.93 (s, 3H), 2.23 (d, $J = 1.3$ Hz, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 148.11, 143.39, 141.92, 128.60, 128.31, 125.88, 119.75, 61.98, 16.44. HRMS-TOF calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 198.0889, found 198.0852.

(2E)-2-Methyl-5-phenylpent-2-enal O-methyl oxime (3a)

Prepared from (*E*)-2-methyl-5-phenylpent-2-enal (0.750 g, 4.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *O*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.971 g, 11.63 mmol, 2.7 equiv.); Eluent 100:1 pentane/diethyl ether. A colorless oil is obtained (0.651 g, 3.48 mmol, 81% yield). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.65 (s, 1H), 7.35 – 7.25 (m, 2H), 7.25 – 7.14 (m, 3H), 5.72 (t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 1H), 3.87 (s, 3H), 2.73 (t, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 2H), 2.52 (q, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 1H), 1.78 (s, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 153.43, 141.49, 137.77, 131.42, 128.53, 126.15, 61.75, 35.34, 30.15, 11.56. HRMS-TOF calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 226.1202, found 226.0935.

(2E)-3-Methyl-5-phenylpent-2-enal O-methyl oxime (4a)

Prepared from (*E*)-3-methyl-5-phenylpent-2-enal (0.600 g, 2.44 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *O*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.776 g, 9.30 mmol, 2.7 equiv.); Eluent 100:1

pentane/diethyl ether. A colorless oil is obtained (0.425 g, 2.27 mmol, 93% yield). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.01 (d, $J = 10.3$ Hz, 1H, major), 7.88 (d, $J = 10.5$ Hz, 1H, minor), 7.33 – 7.24 (m, 2H), 7.17 (m, 3H), 5.97 – 5.88 (m, 1H), 3.87 (s, 3H, major), 3.84 (s, 3H, minor), 2.83 – 2.69 (m, 2H), 2.46 (m, 2H), 1.88 (d, $J = 1.4$ Hz, 3H, minor), 1.85 (d, $J = 1.3$ Hz, 3H, major). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 147.75, 147.21, 146.89, 141.55, 141.32, 128.60, 128.56, 128.46, 128.43, 126.29, 126.16, 119.29, 118.37, 61.74, 61.70, 41.91, 34.97, 34.85, 34.20, 24.48, 17.50. HRMS-TOF calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 226.1202, found 226.1230.

(2E)-2-Methyl-3-(naphthalen-2-yl)acrylaldehyde O-methyl oxime (5a)

Prepared from (*E*)-2-methyl-3-(naphthalen-2-yl)acrylaldehyde (0.400 g, 2.038 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *O*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.460 mg, 5.50 mmol, 2.7 equiv.); Eluent 60:1 pentane/diethyl ether. White fluffy crystals are obtained (0.272 g, 1.21 mmol, 59% yield). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.90 (d, $J = 0.7$ Hz, 1H), 7.87 – 7.78 (m, 4H), 7.55 – 7.43 (m, 3H), 6.78 (dd, $J = 2.0, 1.0$ Hz, 1H), 3.96 (s, 3H), 2.21 (d, $J = 1.3$ Hz, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 153.91, 136.27, 134.24, 133.35, 132.67, 132.65, 128.69, 128.29, 127.97, 127.77, 127.32, 126.47, 126.45, 62.05, 13.46. HRMS-TOF calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 248.1046, found 248.1044.

(2E)-3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-2-methylacrylaldehyde O-methyl oxime (6a)

Prepared from (*E*)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2-methylacrylaldehyde (0.450 g, 2.55 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *O*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.576 g, 6.90 mmol, 2.7 equiv.); Eluent 60:1 pentane/diethyl ether. A colorless oil is obtained (0.460 g, 2.25 mmol, 88% yield). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.82 (s, 1H), 7.32 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 2H), 6.91 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 6.56 (s, 1H), 3.92 (s, 3H), 3.83 (s, 3H), 2.11 (d, $J = 1.3$ Hz, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 159.13, 154.19, 135.99, 130.90, 130.43, 129.41, 113.93, 61.93, 55.43, 13.28. HRMS-TOF calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 228.0995, found 228.0995.

(2E)-3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2-methylacrylaldehyde O-methyl oxime (7a)

Prepared from (*E*)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-methylacrylaldehyde (0.693 g, 3.84 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *O*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.865 g, 10.37 mmol, 2.7 equiv.); Eluent 60:1 pentane/diethyl ether. A white solid is obtained (0.767 g, 3.66 mmol, 95% yield). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.81 (s, 1H), 7.37 – 7.26 (m, 4H), 6.56 (s, 1H), 3.93 (s, 3H), 2.09 (d, $J = 1.3$ Hz, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 153.50, 135.14, 134.76, 133.43, 132.94, 130.68, 128.67, 62.08, 13.28. HRMS-TOF calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{ClNO}$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 232.0500, found 232.0919.

(2E)-2-Methyl-3-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)acrylaldehyde O-methyl oxime (8a)

Prepared from (*E*)-2-methyl-3-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)acrylaldehyde (0.547 g, 2.55 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *O*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.576 g, 6.59 mmol, 2.7 equiv.); Eluent 60:1 pentane/diethyl ether. A white solid is obtained (0.460 g, 2.41 mmol, 95% yield). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.83 (s, 1H), 7.62 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 2H), 7.45 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 2H), 6.63 (s, 1H), 3.94 (s, 3H), 2.11 (d, *J* = 1.3 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 153.16, 140.23, 134.48, 134.32, 129.57, 125.43, 125.40, 125.36, 125.32, 62.17, 13.33. ¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -62.60. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₂H₁₂F₃NO [M+Na]⁺ 266.0763, found 266.1488.

(2E)-2-Methyl-3-(thiophen-2-yl)acrylaldehyde O-methyl oxime (9a)

Prepared from (*E*)-2-methyl-3-(thiophen-2-yl)acrylaldehyde (0.541 g, 3.55 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *O*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.802 g, 9.60 mmol, 2.7 equiv.); Eluent 60:1 pentane/diethyl ether. A yellowish solid is obtained (0.581 g, 3.21 mmol, 90% yield). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.80 (d, *J* = 0.7 Hz, 1H), 7.39 (d, *J* = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 7.13 (d, *J* = 3.6 Hz, 1H), 7.07 (dd, *J* = 5.1, 3.6 Hz, 1H), 6.76 (dd, *J* = 1.3, 0.7 Hz, 1H), 3.93 (s, 3H), 2.21 (d, *J* = 1.2 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 153.39, 140.21, 129.74, 129.40, 128.93, 127.47, 127.30, 62.04, 13.41. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₉H₁₁NOS [M+Na]⁺ 204.0454, found 204.0428.

2-((*E*)-Benzylidene)butanal O-methyl oxime (10a)

Prepared from (*E*)-2-benzylidenebutanal (0.808 g, 5.04 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *O*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.137 g, 13.61 mmol, 2.7 equiv.); Eluent 60:1 pentane/diethyl ether. A colorless oil is obtained (0.673 g, 3.56 mmol, 71% yield). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.74 (s, 1H), 7.39 – 7.27 (m, 5H), 6.56 (s, 1H), 3.93 (s, 3H), 2.59 (q, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 2H), 1.23 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 152.76, 138.57, 136.65, 135.62, 129.06, 128.55, 127.65, 62.02, 20.18, 13.68. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₂H₁₅NO [M+Na]⁺ 212.1046, found 212.1062.

(2E)-2,3-Diphenylacrylaldehyde O-methyl oxime (11a)

Prepared from (*E*)-2,3-diphenylacrylaldehyde (0.069 g, 0.33 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *O*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.075 g, 0.90 mmol, 2.7 equiv.); Eluent 60:1 pentane/diethyl ether. A white solid is obtained (0.057 g, 0.24 mmol, 72% yield). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.01 (d, *J* = 0.6 Hz, 1H), 7.37 – 7.34 (m, 3H), 7.25 – 7.22 (m, 2H), 7.15 – 7.10 (m, 3H), 6.98 – 6.94 (m, 2H), 6.77 (s, 1H), 3.83 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 153.55, 136.30, 136.27, 136.16, 135.85, 129.96, 129.79, 128.68, 128.22, 128.00, 127.87, 62.11. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₆H₁₅NO [M+Na]⁺ 260.1016, found 260.1046.

(*E*)-2,5-Dimethylhex-2-enal *O*-methyl oxime (12a)

Prepared from (*E*)-2,5-dimethylhex-2-enal (0.360 g, 2.85 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *O*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.643 g, 7.70 mmol, 2.7 equiv.); Eluent 100:1 pentane/diethyl ether. A colorless oil is obtained (0.181 g, 1.17 mmol, 41% yield). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.67 (s, 1H), 5.70 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 1H), 3.87 (s, 3H), 2.07 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 3H), 1.81 (d, *J* = 0.7 Hz, 1H), 1.69 (dp, *J* = 13.5, 6.7 Hz, 6H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 153.76, 138.27, 131.29, 61.71, 37.40, 28.77, 22.54, 11.74. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₉H₁₇NO [M+Na]⁺ 178.1202, found 178.1151.

(*E*)-3-Cyclohexyl-2-methylacrylaldehyde *O*-methyl oxime (13a)

Prepared from (*E*)-3-cyclohexyl-2-methylacrylaldehyde (0.558 g, 3.67 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *O*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.827 g, 9.91 mmol, 2.7 equiv.); Eluent 120:1 pentane/diethyl ether. A colorless oil is obtained (0.270 g, 1.49 mmol, 41% yield). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.13 (s, 1H), 5.52 (d, *J* = 9.7 Hz, 1H), 3.89 (s, 3H), 2.47 – 2.27 (m, 1H), 1.84 (s, 3H), 1.75 – 1.56 (m, 5H), 1.31 – 0.99 (m, 5H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 147.94, 143.15, 126.70, 61.81, 36.64, 33.50, 25.96, 25.87, 19.08. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₁H₁₉NO [M+Na]⁺ 204.1359, found 204.1324.

(*E*)-3-(4-(*tert*-Butyl)phenyl)-2-methylacrylaldehyde *O*-methyl oxime (E-14a)

Prepared from (*E*)-3-(4-(*tert*-butyl)phenyl)-2-methylacrylaldehyde (0.676 g, 3.34 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and *O*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.754 g, 9.02 mmol, 2.7 equiv.); Eluent 100:1 pentane/diethyl ether. A white solid is obtained (0.556 g, 3.17 mmol, 95% yield). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.83 (s, 1H), 7.40 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.32 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 6.60 (s, 1H), 3.92 (s, 3H), 2.13 (d, *J* = 1.3 Hz, 3H), 1.33 (s, 9H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 154.14, 150.82, 136.23, 133.91, 131.60, 129.30, 125.41, 61.97, 34.79, 31.40, 13.35. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₅H₂₁NO [M+Na]⁺ 254.1515, found 254.1472.

(*Z*)-3-(4-(*tert*-Butyl)phenyl)-2-methylacrylaldehyde *O*-methyl oxime (Z-14a)

Prepared from **Z-14** (0.691 g, 3.42 mmol, 1 equiv.) and *O*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.770 g, 9.22 mmol, 2.7 equiv.); Eluent 150:1 pentane/diethyl ether. A colorless oil is obtained (0.575 g, 3.28 mmol, 96% yield). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.15 (d, *J* = 0.9 Hz, 1H), 7.35 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 2H), 7.22 – 7.09 (m, 2H), 6.77 (s, 1H), 3.90 (s, 3H), 2.06 (d, *J* = 1.4 Hz, 3H), 1.32 (s, 9H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 150.58, 149.15, 135.08, 133.50, 130.49, 129.09, 125.37, 61.95, 34.72, 31.42, 19.60. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₅H₂₁NO [M+Na]⁺ 254.1515, found 254.1495.

Synthesis of other intermediates and substrates

(2E)-2-methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde oxime (1ad)

Prepared from (*E*)-2-methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde (0.500 g, 3.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.259 g, 3.72 mmol, 1.2 equiv.) by following a reported procedure.³⁵ The spectroscopic data is in accordance with the literature; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.91 (d, *J* = 0.7 Hz, 1H), 7.50 (s, 1H), 7.41 – 7.34 (m, 4H), 7.32 – 7.26 (m, 1H), 6.69 (s, 1H), 2.10 (d, *J* = 1.3 Hz, 3H).³⁶

(2E)-2-Methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde *O*-acetyl oxime (1adAc)

A predried flask is charged with (*E*)-2-methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde oxime (0.300 g, 1.86 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), acetic anhydride (0.400 g, 3.92 mmol, 2.1 equiv.) and pyridine (10 mL). The flask is stoppered, and the reaction is stirred at room temperature overnight. After completion, indicated by TLC, to the cooled reaction mixture diethyl ether is added and the solution quenched with solid NaHCO₃ followed by a sequential wash with distilled water (10 mL) and brine (10 mL). After drying and evaporation the crude product is purified by silica gel flash chromatography (eluent 60:1 pentane/diethyl ether). A colorless oil is obtained (0.299 g, 1.47 mmol, 79% yield). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.10 (d, *J* = 0.4 Hz, 1H), 7.42 – 7.29 (m, 5H), 6.83 (s, 1H), 2.21 (d, *J* = 1.1 Hz, 6H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 169.02, 160.86, 141.09, 135.84, 131.27, 129.66, 128.60, 128.49, 19.79, 13.29. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₂H₁₃NO₂ [M+Na]⁺ 226.0838, found 226.0831.

(*E*)-2-(1-phenylprop-1-en-2-yl)-1,3-dioxolane (1ae)

A round-bottom flask is charged with (*E*)-2-methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde (1.000 g, 6.84 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), ethylene glycol (2.123 g, 24.20 mmol, 5.0 equiv.), *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (0.013 g, 0.07 mmol, 0.01 equiv.) and toluene (40 mL). A Dean-Stark head is connected, and the reaction is boiled overnight. After completion, indicated by TLC, the cooled reaction mixture is washed sequentially with distilled water (10 mL), saturated NaHCO₃ solution (10 mL), distilled water (10 mL) and finally, brine (10 mL). After drying and evaporation the crude product is purified by silica gel gravity chromatography (eluent 100:1 pentane/diethyl ether). A colorless oil is obtained (0.448 g, 2.35 mmol, 34% yield). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.39 – 7.22 (m, 5H), 6.68 (s, 1H), 5.29 (s, 1H), 4.14 – 3.95 (m, 4H), 1.88 (d, *J* = 1.4 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 136.90, 134.60, 130.14, 129.22, 128.27, 127.11, 107.82, 65.62, 12.01. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₂H₁₄O₂ [M+Na]⁺ 215.1043, found 215.1025.

2-Benzylacrylaldehyde (**t1**)

Prepared from 3-phenylpropanal (1.000 g, 7.45 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) by following a reported procedure.³⁶ The spectroscopic data is in accordance with the literature; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 9.61 (s, 1H), 7.33 – 7.16 (m, 5H), 6.11 (q, *J* = 1.1 Hz, 1H), 6.07 (q, *J* = 0.9 Hz, 1H), 3.57 (s, 2H).³⁷

(*Z*)-3-(4-(*tert*-Butyl)phenyl)-2-methylacrylaldehyde (**Z-14**)

An *E/Z* mixture of ethyl 3-(4-(*tert*-butyl)phenyl)-2-methylacrylate is obtained after isomerizing (*E*)-3-(4-(*tert*-butyl)phenyl)-2-methylacrylate (3.000 g, 12.18 mmol, 1.0 equiv., prepared by following General procedure I) with blue light by following a reported procedure.³⁸ The colorless oil obtained after purification is a diastereoisomeric mixture with a 5:7 *E/Z* ratio (2.442 g, 9.91 mmol, 81% yield). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.66 (d, *J* = 1.6 Hz, 1H), 7.45 – 7.28 (m, 5H), 7.22 – 7.16 (m, 3H), 6.67 (d, *J* = 1.8 Hz, 1H), 4.27 (q, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 1H, minor), 4.14 (q, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 2H, major), 2.14 (d, *J* = 1.5 Hz, 3H, minor), 2.09 (d, *J* = 1.6 Hz, 3H, major), 1.36 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 3H, minor), 1.34 (s, 9H, minor), 1.31 (s, 9H, major), 1.12 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H, major). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 169.97, 169.03, 151.67, 150.80, 138.70, 134.45, 133.57, 133.26, 129.73, 129.50, 128.09, 127.95, 125.46, 125.06, 60.95, 60.67, 34.86, 34.71, 31.41, 31.37, 21.66, 14.49, 14.26, 13.93.

The ester mixture (1.800 g, 7.31 mmol, 1 equiv.) is reduced to the corresponding allylic alcohol by following General procedure I. A colorless oil is obtained (1.478 g, 7.23 mmol, 99% yield). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.36 (t, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 4H), 7.25 – 7.21 (m, 1H), 7.18 – 7.12 (m, 3H), 6.49 (s, 1H, minor), 6.43 (s, 1H, major), 4.30 (d, *J* = 4.1 Hz, 2H, major), 4.19 (d, *J* = 4.9 Hz, 2H, minor), 2.00 (d, *J* = 1.6 Hz, 3H, major), 1.93 (d, *J* = 1.3 Hz, 3H, minor), 1.33 (s, 9H, minor), 1.32 (s, 9H, major). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 149.72, 149.53, 137.15, 137.12, 134.77, 134.49, 128.74, 128.53, 128.40, 125.25, 125.21, 125.13, 69.40, 62.56, 34.64, 31.47, 21.95, 15.51.

Finally, the allylic alcohol (1.470 g, 7.19 mmol, 1 equiv., 5:7 *E/Z*) is oxidized without any prior purification by following General procedure I. The crude product is purified by gravitational chromatography (40:1 pentane/diethyl ether) to yield pure (*Z*)-3-(4-(*tert*-butyl)phenyl)-2-methylacrylaldehyde (**Z-14**) as a slightly yellow oil (0.691 g, 3.42 mmol, 81% yield in terms of *Z*). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 9.93 (s, 1H), 7.57 (s, 1H), 7.44 – 7.38 (m, 2H), 7.24 (s, 1H), 1.97 (d, *J* = 1.5 Hz, 3H), 1.34 (s, 9H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 193.48, 152.43, 146.30, 137.35, 131.51, 129.90, 125.52, 34.90, 31.36, 16.89. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₄H₁₈O [M+Na]⁺ 225.1250, found 225.1231.

General procedure III. Asymmetric hydrogenations

A predried glass vial is charged with the appropriate substrate (1.0 equiv.), preprepared chiral catalyst^a (Fig. S1, 0.01-0.05 equiv.) and toluene (2 mL). The vial is placed in the reactor system and stirred overnight at an appropriate temperature and hydrogen pressure. After completion, the reaction mixture is filtered through a silica gel plug (eluent 1:1 pentane/diethyl ether) to yield the corresponding hydrogenated product. The chromatographic data and racemate preparations are tabulated in Table S1.

Figure S1. Structures of the chiral catalysts used in the following reports.

(*S*)-2-Methyl-3-phenylpropanal *O*-methyl oxime (**1b**)

Prepared from **1a** (110.00 mg, 0.628 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **A** (10.28 mg, 0.0063 mmol, 0.01 equiv.) at 40 °C and 10 bar of hydrogen pressure. A colorless oil is obtained (110.00 mg, 0.626 mmol, 99% yield, 99% conv., >99% ee). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.36 – 7.25 (m, 3H), 7.25 – 7.10 (m, 2H), 3.80 (s, 3H), 2.85 (dd, *J* = 12.8, 5.9 Hz, 1H), 2.74 – 2.51 (m, 2H), 1.06 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 154.58, 139.41, 129.34, 128.49, 126.35, 61.37, 41.11, 36.26, 17.66. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₁H₁₅NO [M+Na]⁺ 200.1046, found 200.1089. [α]_D²⁴ = + 34.000 (c = 0.1, CHCl₃).

(*S*)-2-Methyl-3-phenylpropanal *O*-ethyl oxime (**1ba**)

Prepared from **1aa** (32.00 mg, 0.183 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **A** (1.50 mg, 0.0018 mmol, 0.01 equiv.) at 40 °C and 10 bar of hydrogen pressure. A colorless oil is obtained (31.00 mg, 0.178 mmol, 97% yield, 99% conv., >99% ee). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.29 (dd, *J* = 15.9, 7.2 Hz, 3H), 7.21 – 7.14 (m, 2H), 4.04 (q, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 2H), 2.85 (dd, *J* = 12.9, 6.1 Hz, 1H), 2.73 – 2.54 (m, 2H), 1.21 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 3H), 1.06 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 154.32, 139.51, 129.35, 128.47, 126.31, 69.05, 41.14, 36.37, 17.74, 14.60. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₂H₁₇NO [M+Na]⁺ 214.1202, found 214.1249. [α]_D²⁴ = + 32.000 (c = 0.1, CHCl₃).

^a The opposite enantiomers of the catalysts are denoted as **A'**, **B'**, **C'**, and **D'**, if used.

(S)-2-Methyl-3-phenylpropanal *O*-(*tert*-butyl) oxime (**1bb**)

Prepared from **1ab** (20.00 mg, 0.092 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **A** (3.00 mg, 0.0018 mmol, 0.02 equiv.) at 40 °C and 10 bar of hydrogen pressure. A mixture of the product and starting material is obtained as a colorless oil (18.00 mg, 74% conv.). The NMR spectra are reported stacked with the ones for the starting material. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₄H₂₁NO [M+Na]⁺ 242.1515, found 242.1584. [α]_D²² = + 8.000 (c = 0.1, CHCl₃, reported as a mixture).

(S)-2-Methyl-3-phenylpropanal *O*-benzyl oxime (**1bc**)

Prepared from **1ac** (23.00 mg, 0.092 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **A** (3.00 mg, 0.0018 mmol, 0.02 equiv.) at 40 °C and 10 bar of hydrogen pressure. A colorless oil is obtained (23.00 mg, 0.091 mmol, 99% yield, >99% conv., 91% ee obtained after ozonolysis to **1cOH**). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.40 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H), 7.37 – 7.26 (m, 7H), 7.24 – 7.18 (m, 1H), 7.17 – 7.12 (m, 2H), 5.04 (s, 2H), 2.84 (dd, *J* = 13.0, 6.3 Hz, 1H), 2.75 – 2.56 (m, 2H), 1.07 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.10, 139.43, 137.85, 129.33, 128.51, 128.47, 128.33, 127.90, 126.32, 75.71, 41.06, 36.32, 17.74. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₇H₁₉NO [M+Na]⁺ 276.1359, found 276.1450. [α]_D²⁷ = + 21.000 (c = 0.1, CHCl₃).

2-(1-Phenylpropan-2-yl)-1,3-dioxolane (**1be**)

Prepared from **1ae** (24.00 mg, 0.126 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **B** (2.02 mg, 0.0013 mmol, 0.01 equiv.) in the presence of K₂CO₃ (0.72 mg, 0.005 mmol, 0.04 equiv.) at 60 °C and 40 bar of hydrogen pressure. A colorless oil is obtained after filtering through a basic alumina plug (19.30 mg, 0.100 mmol, 79% yield, >99% conv., 96% ee). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, C₆D₆) δ 7.15 – 7.06 (m, 5H), 4.68 (d, *J* = 4.1 Hz, 1H), 3.56 – 3.48 (m, 2H), 3.39 – 3.31 (m, 2H), 3.04 (dd, *J* = 13.4, 5.0 Hz, 1H), 2.46 (dd, *J* = 13.4, 9.5 Hz, 1H), 2.19 – 2.07 (m, 1H), 1.00 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, C₆D₆) δ 140.94, 129.62, 128.59, 126.16, 107.03, 65.08, 39.49, 38.30, 13.71. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₂H₁₆O₂ [M+Na]⁺ 215.1043, found 215.1025. [α]_D²³ = + 9.000 (c = 0.1, CHCl₃).

3-Phenylbutanal *O*-methyl oxime (**2b**)

Prepared from **2a** (9.30 mg, 0.052 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **D** (1.57 mg, 0.0010 mmol, 0.02 equiv.) at 60 °C and 50 bar of hydrogen pressure. A mixture of the product and starting material is obtained as a colorless oil (6.50 mg, 28% conv., 92% ee). The NMR spectra are reported stacked with the ones for the starting material. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₁H₁₅NO [M+Na]⁺ 200.1046, found 200.1105.

(S)-2-Methyl-5-phenylpentanal *O*-methyl oxime (3b)

Prepared from **3a** (30.00 mg, 0.150 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **C** (2.40 mg, 0.0015 mmol, 0.01 equiv.) at 40 °C and 10 bar of hydrogen pressure. A colorless oil is obtained (28.00 mg, 0.140 mmol, 93% yield, 99% conv., 95% ee). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.34 – 7.25 (m, 1H), 7.22 – 7.13 (m, 4H), 3.81 (s, 3H), 2.61 (td, *J* = 7.4, 2.0 Hz, 2H), 2.50 – 2.28 (m, 1H), 1.64 (td, *J* = 8.3, 7.4 Hz, 2H), 1.53 – 1.37 (m, 2H), 1.07 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.24, 142.41, 128.54, 128.44, 125.88, 61.33, 35.95, 34.46, 34.43, 29.03, 18.40. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₃H₁₉NO [M+Na]⁺ 228.1359, found 228.1395. [α]_D²⁴ = + 17.000 (c = 0.1, CHCl₃).

3-Methyl-5-phenylpentanal *O*-methyl oxime (4b)

Prepared from **4a** (10.00 mg, 0.049 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **D** (3.87 mg, 0.0025 mmol, 0.05 equiv.) at 60 °C and 40 bar of hydrogen pressure. A mixture of the product and starting material is obtained as a colorless oil (7.00 mg, 73% conv., 89% ee). The NMR spectra are reported stacked with the ones for the starting material. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₃H₁₉NO [M+Na]⁺ 228.1359, found 228.1360.

(S)-2-Methyl-3-(naphthalen-2-yl)propanal *O*-methyl oxime (5b)

Prepared from **5a** (20.00 mg, 0.089 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **D** (2.90 mg, 0.0018 mmol, 0.02 equiv.) at 40 °C and 10 bar of hydrogen pressure. A colorless oil is obtained (20.00 mg, 0.088 mmol, 99% yield, >99% conv., 96% ee). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.84 – 7.75 (m, 3H), 7.61 (s, 1H), 7.51 – 7.39 (m, 2H), 7.36 (d, *J* = 6.3 Hz, 1H), 7.31 (dd, *J* = 8.4, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 3.80 (s, 3H), 3.07 – 2.97 (m, 1H), 2.84 – 2.72 (m, 2H), 1.10 (d, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 154.52, 136.97, 133.65, 132.31, 128.10, 127.79, 127.76, 127.74, 127.65, 126.11, 125.49, 61.39, 41.25, 36.23, 17.75. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₅H₁₇NO [M+Na]⁺ 250.1202, found 250.1175. [α]_D²⁴ = + 27.000 (c = 0.1, CHCl₃).

(S)-3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-2-methylpropanal *O*-methyl oxime (6b)

Prepared from **6a** (20.00 mg, 0.097 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **A** (3.30 mg, 0.0020 mmol, 0.02 equiv.) at 40 °C and 10 bar of hydrogen pressure. A colorless oil is obtained (18.10 mg, 0.089 mmol, 91% yield, >99% conv., 99% ee). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.29 (d, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 1H), 7.09 – 7.05 (m, 2H), 6.84 – 6.81 (m, 2H), 3.80 (s, 3H), 3.79 (s, 3H), 2.78 (dd, *J* = 13.0, 6.0 Hz, 1H), 2.67 – 2.49 (m, 2H), 1.05 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 158.20, 154.72, 131.44, 130.26, 113.91, 61.36, 55.39, 40.24, 36.43, 17.61. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₂H₁₇NO₂ [M+Na]⁺ 230.1151, found 230.1126. [α]_D²⁴ = + 26.000 (c = 0.1, CHCl₃).

(S)-3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2-methylpropanal O-methyl oxime (7b)

Prepared from **7a** (20.00 mg, 0.095 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **A** (3.10 mg, 0.0019 mmol, 0.02 equiv.) at 40 °C and 10 bar of hydrogen pressure. A colorless oil is obtained (21.60 mg, 0.094 mmol, 99% yield, >99% conv., 97% ee). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.29 – 7.23 (m, 3H), 7.11 – 7.06 (m, 2H), 3.79 (s, 3H), 2.85 – 2.76 (m, 1H), 2.69 – 2.53 (m, 2H), 1.05 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 154.10, 137.90, 132.17, 130.66, 128.62, 61.43, 40.37, 36.20, 17.70. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₁H₁₄ClNO [M+Na]⁺ 234.0656, found 234.0633. [α]_D²⁴ = + 40.000 (c = 0.1, CHCl₃).

(S)-2-Methyl-3-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)propanal O-methyl oxime (8b)

Prepared from **8a** (20.00 mg, 0.082 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **A** (2.70 mg, 0.0016 mmol, 0.02 equiv.) at 40 °C and 10 bar of hydrogen pressure. A colorless oil is obtained (20.00 mg, 0.081 mmol, 99% yield, >99% conv., 98% ee). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.55 (s, 1H), 7.53 (s, 1H), 7.28 (d, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 3H), 3.79 (s, 3H), 2.96 – 2.85 (m, 1H), 2.74 – 2.62 (m, 2H), 1.07 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 153.81, 143.63, 129.64, 125.50, 125.46, 125.42, 125.38, 61.46, 40.76, 36.09, 17.78. ¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -62.39. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₂H₁₄F₃NO [M+Na]⁺ 268.0920, found 268.0894. [α]_D²⁴ = + 36.000 (c = 0.1, CHCl₃).

(S)-2-Methyl-3-(thiophen-2-yl)propanal O-methyl oxime (9b)

Prepared from **9a** (15.00 mg, 0.083 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **D** (3.90 mg, 0.0025 mmol, 0.03 equiv.) at 40 °C and 10 bar of hydrogen pressure. A colorless oil is obtained (13.50 mg, 0.074 mmol, 89% yield, >99% conv.). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.32 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H), 7.14 (dd, *J* = 5.1, 1.2 Hz, 1H), 6.92 (dd, *J* = 5.2, 3.4 Hz, 1H), 6.83 – 6.78 (m, 1H), 3.81 (s, 3H), 3.04 (dd, *J* = 14.7, 6.7 Hz, 1H), 2.86 (dd, *J* = 14.7, 7.6 Hz, 1H), 2.69 (p, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 1H), 1.12 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 153.96, 141.83, 126.92, 125.81, 123.86, 61.44, 36.61, 34.93, 17.77. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₉H₁₃NOS [M+Na]⁺ 206.0610, found 206.0694. [α]_D²² = + 16.000 (c = 0.1, CHCl₃).

(S)-2-Benzylbutanal O-methyl oxime (10b)

Prepared from **10a** (30.00 mg, 0.159 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **A** (2.60 mg, 0.0016 mmol, 0.01 equiv.) at 40 °C and 10 bar of hydrogen pressure. A colorless oil is obtained (29.50 mg, 0.154 mmol, 97% yield, >99% conv., >99% ee). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.31 – 7.13 (m, 5H), 3.79 (s, 3H), 2.79 (dd, *J* = 13.8, 7.3 Hz, 1H), 2.70 (dd, *J* = 13.7, 7.3 Hz, 1H), 2.54 – 2.43 (m, 1H), 1.59 – 1.47 (m, 1H), 1.40 (ddd, *J* = 13.9, 8.8, 7.2 Hz, 1H), 0.91 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 153.83, 139.46, 129.37, 128.47, 126.28, 61.39, 43.04,

39.30, 25.21, 11.60. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₂H₁₇NO [M+Na]⁺ 214.1202, found 214.1203. [α]_D²⁷ = + 27.000 (c = 0.1, CHCl₃).

(S)-2,3-Diphenylpropanal O-methyl oxime (11b)

Prepared from **11a** (20.00 mg, 0.084 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **A** (2.80 mg, 0.0017 mmol, 0.02 equiv.) at 40 °C and 10 bar of hydrogen pressure. A colorless oil is obtained (20.50 mg, 0.083 mmol, 99% yield, >99% conv., 91% ee). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.53 (d, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 1H), 7.30 – 7.11 (m, 8H), 7.06 – 7.02 (m, 2H), 3.81 (s, 3H), 3.77 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 1H), 3.25 (dd, *J* = 13.7, 7.1 Hz, 1H), 3.03 (dd, *J* = 13.7, 8.0 Hz, 1H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 152.12, 140.46, 139.12, 129.41, 128.77, 128.32, 128.16, 127.12, 126.31, 61.58, 48.24, 40.38. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₆H₁₇NO [M+Na]⁺ 262.1202, found 262.1204. [α]_D²⁴ = - 53.000 (c = 0.1, CHCl₃).

(S)-2,5-Dimethylhexanal O-methyl oxime (12b)

Prepared from **12a** (10.00 mg, 0.089 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **D** (2.99 mg, 0.0019 mmol, 0.05 equiv.) at 40 °C and 10 bar of hydrogen pressure. A mixture of the product and starting material is obtained as a colorless oil (6.30 mg, 92% conv., >99% ee). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.21 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 3.81 (s, 3H), 2.30 (dt, *J* = 14.0, 7.0 Hz, 1H), 1.55 – 1.46 (m, 1H), 1.45 – 1.32 (m, 2H), 1.19 (ddd, *J* = 9.8, 6.5, 2.6 Hz, 2H), 1.06 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H), 0.87 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 6H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.65, 61.30, 36.37, 34.76, 32.76, 28.21, 22.71, 22.66, 18.45. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₉H₁₉NO [M+Na]⁺ 180.1359, found 180.1350. [α]_D²⁷ = + 9.000 (c = 0.1, CHCl₃, reported as a mixture).

(S)-3-Cyclohexyl-2-methylpropanal O-methyl oxime (13b)

Prepared from **13a** (15.00 mg, 0.082 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **A** (6.60 mg, 0.0041 mmol, 0.05 equiv.) at 40 °C and 10 bar of hydrogen pressure. A colorless oil in a 1:3 diastereomeric mixture is obtained (11.90 mg, 0.065 mmol, 79% yield, >99% conv., 34% ee). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.18 (d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H, major), 6.40 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H, minor), 3.83 (s, 3H, minor), 3.80 (s, 1H, major), 3.21 – 3.10 (m, 1H, minor), 2.47 (p, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 1H, major), 1.73 – 1.61 (m, 4H), 1.36 – 1.08 (m, 7H), 1.03 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H, major), 0.98 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H, minor), 0.94 – 0.82 (m, 2H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 157.16, 155.84, 61.62, 61.28, 42.86, 42.69, 35.57, 35.04, 33.74, 33.58, 33.34, 33.30, 31.63, 27.60, 26.76, 26.74, 26.42, 26.39, 26.37, 18.78, 18.15. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₁H₂₁NO [M+Na]⁺ 206.1515, found 206.1525. [α]_D²⁷ = + 5.000 (c = 0.1, CHCl₃).

(S)-3-(4-(*tert*-Butyl)phenyl)-2-methylpropanal *O*-methyl oxime (E-14b)

Prepared from **E-14a** (80.00 mg, 0.350 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **D** (11.05 mg, 0.0070 mmol, 0.02 equiv.) at 40 °C and 10 bar of hydrogen pressure. A colorless oil is obtained (80.10 mg, 0.340 mmol, 98% yield, 99% conv, 98% ee). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.31 (dd, *J* = 7.4, 3.7 Hz, 3H), 7.09 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 2H), 3.80 (s, 3H), 2.81 (dd, *J* = 13.1, 6.1 Hz, 1H), 2.66 (dq, *J* = 8.2, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 2.57 (dd, *J* = 13.1, 8.1 Hz, 1H), 1.31 (s, 9H), 1.06 (d, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 154.82, 149.14, 136.27, 128.99, 125.37, 61.35, 40.59, 36.20, 34.52, 31.53, 17.68. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₅H₂₃NO [M+Na]⁺ 256.1672, found 256.1684. [α]_D²⁷ = + 34.000 (c = 0.1, CHCl₃).

3-(4-(*tert*-Butyl)phenyl)-2-methylpropanal *O*-methyl oxime from Z-14a (Z-14b)

Prepared from **Z-14a** (20 mg, 0.088 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) using catalyst **D** (5.60 mg, 0.0035 mmol, 0.04 equiv.) at 40 °C and 10 bar of hydrogen pressure. A mixture of the product and starting material is obtained as a colorless oil (17.00 mg, 85% conv., 93% ee, the major enantiomer is the same as for **E-14b**). The spectroscopic data is identical to that for compound **E-14b**. HRMS-TOF calcd. for C₁₅H₂₃NO [M+Na]⁺ 256.1672, found 256.1643. [α]_D²⁷ = + 28.000 (c = 0.1, CHCl₃, reported as a mixture).

General procedure IV. Oxime ozonolysis

A glass vial is charged with the appropriate chiral oxime (1.0 equiv.) and methanol (1.5 mL). Freshly generated ozone (full power) is then bubbled through the solution at 0 °C for 30 to 60 seconds.^a The ozone is stopped and through the solution nitrogen is bubbled for 10 seconds. The quenching agent is then swiftly added at 0 °C. Then, the reaction mixture is further stirred for an additional 30 minutes at room temperature. After removing the solvent, the crude product is filtered through a silica gel or alumina plug^b (eluent 1:1 pentane/diethyl ether) to yield the corresponding saturated chiral aldehyde or alcohol. The chromatographic data and racemate preparations are tabulated in Table S1.

(S)-2-Methyl-3-phenylpropanal (1c)

Prepared from **1b** (20.00 mg, 0.112 mmol, 1.0 equiv., >99% ee) with Me₂S (0.5 mL) as the quenching agent. A colorless oil is obtained (14.94 mg, 0.100 mmol, 89% yield, 98% conv., 87% ee with purification, 98% ee without purification). The spectroscopic data is in accordance with the literature; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 9.73 (d, *J* = 1.5 Hz, 1H), 7.31 – 7.27 (m, 2H), 7.23 (d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 1H), 7.21 – 7.16 (m, 2H), 3.10 (dd, *J* = 13.3, 5.4 Hz, 1H), 2.72 – 2.58 (m, 2H), 1.10 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H).^{39a,39b} [α]_D²³ = + 12.000 (*c* = 0.123, CHCl₃).

(S)-2-Methyl-3-phenylpropan-1-ol (1cOH)

Prepared from **1bc** (20.00 mg, 0.079 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) with excess NaBH₄ as the quenching agent. A mixture of the product and starting material is obtained as a slightly yellow oil (9.50 mg, 80% conv., 91% ee). The spectroscopic data is in accordance with the literature; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.29 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H), 7.23 – 7.14 (m, 3H), 3.58 – 3.42 (m, 2H), 2.77 (dd, *J* = 13.4, 6.3 Hz, 1H), 2.43 (dd, *J* = 13.4, 8.1 Hz, 1H), 1.95 (dp, *J* = 8.0, 6.3 Hz, 1H), 1.58 (s, 1H), 0.92 (d, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 3H).^{39c}

(S)-2-methyl-5-phenylpentanal (3c)

Prepared from **3b** (20.00 mg, 0.098 mmol, 1.0 equiv., 91% ee) with Me₂S (0.5 mL) as the quenching agent. A colorless oil is obtained (11.50 mg, 0.065 mmol, 67% yield, 99% conv., 86% ee with purification, 91% ee without purification). The spectroscopic data is in accordance

^a Reactions at a scale of about 0.07 mmol proceeded to full conversion before 30 seconds of ozone. A larger scale of about 0.14 mmol proceeds to full conversion after 60 seconds of ozone bubbling.

^b Analyzing the chiral aldehydes without purification showed a high degree of retention in chirality. After filtering the crude product through a plug of silica gel, neutral or basic alumina partial racemization is observed. Filtering through neutral alumina, however, produced a cleaner product.

with the literature; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.60 (d, $J = 1.9$ Hz, 1H), 7.28 (dd, $J = 8.2$, 6.7 Hz, 2H), 7.22 – 7.15 (m, 3H), 2.64 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H), 2.42 – 2.30 (m, 1H), 1.76 – 1.64 (m, 3H), 1.45 – 1.37 (m, 1H), 1.10 (d, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 3H).^{39d} $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{24} = + 13.000$ ($c = 0.100$, CHCl_3).

(S)-2-Benzylbutanal (10c)

Prepared from **10b** (20.00 mg, 0.104 mmol, 1.0 equiv., 95% ee) with Me_2S (0.5 mL) as the quenching agent. A colorless oil is obtained (14.70 mg, 0.092 mmol, 88% yield, 99% conv., 89% ee with purification, 95% ee without purification). The spectroscopic data is in accordance with the literature; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.68 (d, $J = 2.5$ Hz, 1H), 7.31 – 7.27 (m, 2H), 7.24 – 7.15 (m, 3H), 3.00 (dd, $J = 14.0$, 7.3 Hz, 1H), 2.76 (dd, $J = 12.1$, 7.4 Hz, 1H), 2.62 – 2.54 (m, 1H), 1.74 – 1.56 (m, 2H), 0.98 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 3H).^{39b,39e} $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{22} = + 9.901$ ($c = 0.303$, CHCl_3).

(S)-3-(4-(tert-Butyl)phenyl)-2-methylpropanal (14c)

Prepared from **E-14b** (20.00 mg, 0.086 mmol, 1.0 equiv., 98% ee) with Me_2S (0.5 mL) as the quenching agent. A colorless oil is obtained (16.00 mg, 0.078 mmol, 91% yield, 99% conv., 86% ee with purification, 97% ee without purification). The spectroscopic data is in accordance with the literature; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.72 (d, $J = 1.6$ Hz, 1H), 7.31 (d, $J = 8.3$ Hz, 2H), 7.10 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, 2H), 3.05 (dd, $J = 13.5$, 5.9 Hz, 1H), 2.72 – 2.54 (m, 2H), 1.31 (s, 9H), 1.10 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 3H).^{39f} $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = + 7.500$ ($c = 0.120$, CHCl_3).

Separation of chiral products

Table S1. Enantiomeric excess values, retention times and separation methods.

Product	ee (%)	Retention time		Separation method
		T _{R1} (min)	T _{R2} (min)	
 1b	>99	43.107	43.695	GC-MS: Chiraldex B-DM column, 50-110 °C, 1 °C/min ^a
 1ba	>99	50.634	51.235	GC-MS: Chiraldex B-DM column, 50-110 °C, 1 °C/min ^a
 1be	96	7.358	9.057	SFC: Chiralpak IB column, 5% MeOH, 0.8 mL/min ^a
 2b	92	43.370	43.936	GC-MS: Chiraldex B-DM column, 50-110 °C, 1 °C/min ^a
 3b	95	2.818	3.128	SFC: Chiralcel AY-H column, 5% MeOH, 2 mL/min ^a
 4b	89	3.134	3.444	SFC: Chiralcel AY-H column, 5% MeOH, 2 mL/min ^a
 5b	96	14.267	15.259	SFC: Chiralcel OJ-H column, 5% MeOH, 2 mL/min ^a
 6b	>99	69.892	70.674	GC-MS: Chiraldex B-DM column, 50-170 °C, 1 °C/min ^a
 7b	96	65.067	65.858	GC-MS: Chiraldex B-DM column, 50-170 °C, 1 °C/min ^a
 8b	97	47.548	48.524	GC-MS: Chiraldex B-DM column, 50-170 °C, 1 °C/min ^a
 10b	>99	49.197	49.906	GC-MS: Chiraldex B-DM column, 50-170 °C, 1 °C/min ^a
 11b	91	11.400	12.157	SFC: Chiralpak ID column, 4% MeOH, 1 mL/min ^a
 12b	>99	34.440	34.790	GC-FID: Supelco β-DEX 225 column, 40-100 °C, 1 °C/min ^a

 13b	34	57.660	58.060	GC-FID: Supelco β -DEX 225 column, 50-110 °C, 1 °C/min ^a
 E-14b	98	7.617	8.383	SFC: Chiralcel AY-H column, 4% MeOH, 1 mL/min ^a
 Z-14b	93	6.927	7.782	
 1c	98	64.767	64.980	GC-FID: Supelco β -DEX 225 column, 50-170 °C, 1 °C/min ^a
 1cOH	91	72.310	72.920	GC-FID: Supelco β -DEX 225 column, 50-170 °C, 1 °C/min ^a
 3c	91	174.133	175.017	GC-FID: Supelco β -DEX 225 column, 40-180 °C, 0.5 °C/min ^a
 10c	95	70.980	71.397	GC-FID: Supelco β -DEX 225 column, 50-110 °C, 1 °C/min ^a
 14c	97	174.077	174.837	GC-FID: Supelco β -DEX 225 column, 40-180 °C, 0.5 °C/min ^a

^a The racemate is prepared by subjecting the corresponding unsaturated substrate to hydrogenation (10 bar H₂ for all, 1 bar for preparing racemic **14b**) with Pd/C (10 wt.%) in DCM at room temperature overnight (when unsaturated aldehydes are used, a mixture of the saturated aldehydes and alcohols are observed. The alcohols generally tend to have larger retention times and they show considerable tailing).

Chromatograms

Compound 1b

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	43.140	44529014	1447536	1.793

Compound 1ba

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	50.913	30125186.66	1166343.92	1.104

Compound 1be

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	7.358	6823.30	794.60	0.1431
2	9.057	154.70	13.90	0.1854

Compound 2b

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	43.370	1958984.81	181778.84	0.567
2	43.936	86370.86	10475.88	0.326

Compound 3b

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	2.818	385.91	83.31	0.274
2	3.097	9.98	3.08	0.140

Compound 4b

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	3.134	142.03	23.84	0.232
2	3.444	2427.13	306.57	0.386

Compound 5b

x10² DAD1 - B:Sig=230,4 Ref=off 008-34-572-rac.D

x10³ DAD1 - B:Sig=230,4 Ref=off 007-32-572.D

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	14.267	25239.46	1220.90	0.900
2	15.259	517.74	34.06	0.491

Compound 6b

x10⁴ +EI TIC Scan PAMK-403rac.D

x10⁴ +EI TIC Scan PAMK-403ch.D

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	70.611	1232474.84	64579.43	1.146

Compound 7b

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	65.067	32644.39	1981.58	0.668
2	65.858	1736849.40	76525.09	1.269

Compound 8b

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	47.548	114223.21	8874.28	0.694
2	48.524	7309288.41	280821.88	1.239

Compound 10b

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	49.497	20041001.18	880681.47	1.028

Compound 11b

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	11.400	127.960	7.570	0.619
2	12.157	2840.65	115.52	1.048

Compound 12b

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	34.453	109067.53	13915.62	0.467

Compound 13b

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	57.660	829221.69	92463.31	0.427
2	58.060	404821.59	45828.9	0.390

Compound E-14b

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	7.617	597.45	28.610	0.678
2	8.383	55703.00	1720.08	1.537

Compound Z-14b

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	6.927	1493.82	65.75	0.751
2	7.782	40478.31	1169.18	1.655

Compound 1c (crude product)

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	64.767	18652.22	3408.54	0.173
2	64.980	1737712.88	133712.51	0.680

Compound 1cOH

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	72.310	50562.64	3238.06	0.553
2	72.920	1137964.00	42386.10	1.930

Compound 3c (crude product)

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	174.133	883640.27	46896.51	0.89
2	175.017	40912.04	2377.80	0.55

Compound 10c (crude product)

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	70.980	44669.65	5924.92	0.263
2	71.397	1700164.54	144537.30	0.737

Compound 14c (crude product)

Peak	RT	Area	Height	Width
1	174.077	1501258.58	81694.25	0.947
2	174.837	20687.91	1435.85	0.470

NMR Spectra

(2E)-2-Methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde O-ethyl oxime (1aa)

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3)

(2E)-3-Methyl-5-phenylpent-2-enal O-(tert-butyl) oxime (1ab)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

(2E)-2-Methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde O-benzyl oxime (1ac)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

(2E)-2-methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde O-acetyl oxime (1adAc)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

(E)-2-(1-phenylprop-1-en-2-yl)-1,3-dioxolane (1ae)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

(2E)-3-Methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde O-methyl oxime (2a)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

(2E)-2-Methyl-5-phenylpent-2-enal O-methyl oxime (3a)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

(2E)-3-Methyl-5-phenylpent-2-enal O-methyl oxime (4a)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

(2E)-2-Methyl-3-(naphthalen-2-yl)acrylaldehyde O-methyl oxime (5a)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

(2E)-3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-2-methylacrylaldehyde O-methyl oxime (6a)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

(2E)-3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2-methylacrylaldehyde O-methyl oxime (7a)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

(2E)-2-Methyl-3-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)acrylaldehyde O-methyl oxime (8a)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3)

(2E)-2-Methyl-3-(thiophen-2-yl)acrylaldehyde O-methyl oxime (9a)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

2-((*E*-Benzylidene)butanal *O*-methyl oxime (10a)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

(2E)-2,3-Diphenylacrylaldehyde O-methyl oxime (11a)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

(2E)-2,5-Dimethylhex-2-enal O-methyl oxime (12a)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

(2E)-3-Cyclohexyl-2-methylacrylaldehyde O-methyl oxime (13a)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

(2E)-3-(4-(tert-Butyl)phenyl)-2-methylacrylaldehyde O-methyl oxime (E-14a)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

(2Z)-3-(4-(*tert*-Butyl)phenyl)-2-methylacrylaldehyde *O*-methyl oxime (Z-14a)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

Ethyl (*E/Z*)-3-(4-(*tert*-butyl)phenyl)-2-methylacrylate

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

(E/Z)-3-(4-(*tert*-Butyl)phenyl)-2-methylprop-2-en-1-ol

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

(Z)-3-(4-(*tert*-Butyl)phenyl)-2-methylacrylalde (Z-14)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

2-Methyl-3-phenylpropanal *O*-methyl oxime (1b)

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3)

2-Methyl-3-phenylpropanal *O*-ethyl oxime (1ba)

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3)

2-Methyl-3-phenylpropanal *O*-(*tert*-butyl) oxime (1bb) stacked with 1ab

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3)

2-Methyl-3-phenylpropanal *O*-benzyl oxime (1bc)

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3)

2-(1-Phenylpropan-2-yl)-1,3-dioxolane (1be)

^1H NMR (400 MHz, C_6D_6)

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, C_6D_6)

3-Phenylbutanal *O*-methyl oxime (2b) stacked with 2a

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3)

2-methyl-5-phenylpentanal *O*-methyl oxime (3b)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

3-Methyl-5-phenylpentanal *O*-methyl oxime (4b) stacked with 4a

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3)

2-Methyl-3-(naphthalen-2-yl)propanal *O*-methyl oxime (5b)

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3)

3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-2-methylpropanal *O*-methyl oxime (6b)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃)

3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2-methylpropanal *O*-methyl oxime (7b)

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3)

2-Methyl-3-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)propanal *O*-methyl oxime (8b)

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3)

2-Methyl-3-(thiophen-2-yl)propanal *O*-methyl oxime (9b)

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3)

2-Benzylbutanal *O*-methyl oxime (10b)

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3)

2,3-Diphenylpropanal *O*-methyl oxime (11b)

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3)

2,5-Dimethylhexanal *O*-methyl oxime (12b)

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3)

3-Cyclohexyl-2-methylpropanal *O*-methyl oxime (13b)

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3)

3-(4-(*tert*-Butyl)phenyl)-2-methylpropanal *O*-methyl oxime (E-14b and Z-14b)

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3)

